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integration and deployments**

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym	Description		
<i>AAA</i>	Authentication, Authorization and Accounting	<i>NF</i>	Network Function
<i>AMF</i>	Access and Mobility Management Function	<i>NFVO</i>	NFV Orchestrator
<i>AMQP</i>	Advanced Message Queuing Protocol	<i>NFVI</i>	Network Function Virtualization Infrastructure
<i>API</i>	Application Programming Interface	<i>NLOS</i>	Non-Line of Sight
<i>AR</i>	Augmented Reality	<i>OBUs</i>	On-Board Units
<i>AS</i>	Access Stratum	<i>OAI</i>	OpenAirInterface
<i>BBU</i>	Baseband Unit	<i>O-RU</i>	Open Radio Unit
<i>CNF</i>	Cloud-native Network Function	<i>OSM</i>	Open Source MANO
<i>COTS</i>	Commercial Off-The-Shelf	<i>PCF</i>	Policy Control Function
<i>CP</i>	Control Plane	<i>PDN</i>	Packet Data Network
<i>CRD</i>	Custom Resource Definition (Kubernetes)	<i>PDU</i>	Protocol Data Unit
<i>CU</i>	Central Unit	<i>PLMN</i>	Public Land Mobile Network
<i>DL</i>	Downlink	<i>QoE</i>	Quality of Experience
<i>DNS</i>	Domain Name System	<i>QoS</i>	Quality of Service
<i>DU</i>	Distributed Unit	<i>RA</i>	Radio Access
<i>EPC</i>	Evolved Packet Core	<i>RAN</i>	Radio Access Network
<i>FR1</i>	Frequency Range 1 (5G NR)	<i>RAT</i>	Radio Access Technology
<i>FR2</i>	Frequency Range 2 (mmWave)	<i>RIC</i>	RAN Intelligent Controller
<i>FQDN</i>	Fully Qualified Domain Name	<i>RLC</i>	Radio Link Control
<i>GTP</i>	GPRS Tunnelling Protocol	<i>RU</i>	Radio Unit
<i>HPA</i>	Horizontal Pod Autoscaler	<i>S-NSSAI</i>	Single Network Slice Selection Assistance Information
<i>HTTP/2</i>	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Version 2	<i>SBA</i>	Service-Based Architecture
<i>IAM</i>	Identity and Access Management	<i>SDAP</i>	Service Data Adaptation Protocol
<i>IMS</i>	IP Multimedia Subsystem	<i>SDN</i>	Software Defined Networking
<i>IoS</i>	Internet of Senses	<i>SFI</i>	Slice/Service Function Instance
<i>KPI</i>	Key Performance Indicator	<i>SLA</i>	Service Level Agreement
<i>K8s</i>	Kubernetes	<i>SR-IOV</i>	Single Root I/O Virtualization
<i>MAC</i>	Medium Access Control	<i>SUPI</i>	Subscription Permanent Identifier
<i>MCS</i>	Modulation and Coding Scheme	<i>UE</i>	User Equipment
<i>MEC</i>	Multi-access Edge Computing	<i>UL</i>	Uplink
<i>MNO</i>	Mobile Network Operator	<i>UPF</i>	User Plane Function
<i>MVNO</i>	Mobile Virtual Network Operator	<i>URLLC</i>	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications
<i>NAS</i>	Non-Access Stratum	<i>VR</i>	Virtual Reality
		<i>ZSM</i>	Zero-touch Service Management
		<i>ZTP</i>	Zero Touch Provisioning

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Executive Summary

TrialsNet WP2 focused on the design, development, and deployment of advanced platform and network solutions supporting large-scale 5G and B5G trials across multiple European clusters. These infrastructures serve as the technological backbone enabling the execution of a diverse set of trials in the three domains addressed by the project such as i) Infrastructure, Transportation, Security & Safety, ii) eHealth & Emergency, and iii) Culture, Tourism & Entertainment.

WP2 has been responsible for translating the functional requirements of the use cases (defined in WP3, WP4, and WP5) into integrated and secure infrastructure deployments capable of operating under realistic conditions. It is important to remark that WP2 also carried out activities that were not initially foreseen such as the activities on sustainability and the deployment of mmWave solutions to support the most demanding use cases. In addition, WP2 has worked closely with WP6 to define relevant KPIs and to ensure measurable performance tracking during trials. Based on this consolidated framework, the large-scale validation activities described in this deliverable highlight the technical readiness of the platform and network components, as well as their ability to support heterogeneous and demanding vertical applications. Through extensive field trials in the four clusters located in Italy (which encompasses two sites in Turin and Pisa respectively), Spain, Romania, and Greece, WP2 has consolidated the final design and implementation of end-to-end infrastructures, leveraging commercial-grade hardware and open-source components where applicable. This has included the deployment of standalone 5G infrastructures, advanced edge computing environments, and vertical-specific orchestration platforms, with strong attention to replicability and openness. The main achievements for each cluster are summarized in hereafter.

The **Italian cluster (Turin site)** relied on a commercial 5G Rel-15 network infrastructure, its deployment proved valuable for testing applications with requirements typically associated with Beyond 5G (B5G) systems. The broad coverage and stable performance of the Rel-15 setup allowed the TrialsNet team to validate the different UCs under real-world conditions. By leveraging additional technologies like edge computing and XR platforms co-located with user access, the Turin cluster could emulate some of the characteristics expected from B5G deployments, such as reduced end-to-end latency and improved user Quality of Experience (QoE). Indeed, Rel-15 technology may have exposed limitations (e.g., uplink constraints or capacity bottlenecks during high concurrency), and the trials conducted over Rel-15 infrastructure provided insights into the gaps that future releases need to address.

In the **Italian cluster (Pisa site)** spawns across the CNR campus in Pisa and the Fondazione Monasterio hospital in Massa. More in detail, a private 5G network based on 3GPP Rel-16 SA at 26 GHz (200 MHz bandwidth) has been deployed at the CNR Campus providing both indoor/outdoor coverage for which the compliance of the EMF emission limits requested by the local regulation have been strictly guaranteed. At the same time, the connectivity to the Core Network (CN) in Turin and the hospital in Massa is provided by a specific router connected through VPN (Virtual Private Network). An Ericsson's (ER) Innovative Orchestrator manages end-to-end (i.e., including transport network) quality of service (QoS) of concurrent services through slicing, including mobility aspects. The ER Innovative Orchestrator has been tested with concurrent use cases trials, ensuring service differentiation via dynamic Differentiated Services Code Point (DSCP) and 5G QoS Indicators (5QI) mapping and admission control (AC). Critical patient traffic has been prioritized, maintaining stable performance even under a congestion scenario emulated through "disturbance" traffic. Throughputs up to 900 Mbit/s in downlink and 200 Mbit/s in uplink with 5-15 ms of latency (round-trip) have been achieved.

In the **Spanish cluster**, a private 3GPP Rel-17 SA infrastructure at 26 GHz has been deployed at the Movistar Arena in Madrid. This infrastructure, representing the state-of-the-art of the 3GPP technology (first deployment of this type in Europe), supported the trials of 3 use cases (from the 3 project's domains) during a sport event on the 16/05/2025. The infrastructure covered three different areas; the CN was hosted at the 5TONIC laboratory in Leganes (including also an Edge node). The devices connectivity was provided through 4 CPEs which required a huge tweaking activity to have them properly working being Rel-17 prototypes. The network was configured with 8 Component Carriers (CC) with 800 MHz bandwidth in downlink and 4 CC with 400 MHz bandwidth in uplink, providing throughputs of 3.2 Gbits/sec in downlink and 390 Mbits/sec in uplink, and a latency of few milliseconds. The trial demonstrated a stable and high-performance connectivity achieved in a complex and crowded environment, proving the maturity of 5G mmWave Rel-17 SA technology for commercial deployment.

The **Romanian cluster** integrates 5G SA and NSA hybrid network solutions, Edge Computing, and video analytics. The UC1 (Iasi) and UC4 benefit from a robust design based on both Bucharest and Iasi 5G Labs' resources and an outdoor 5G coverage in the trials' locations. A key innovation is the deployment of a 5G SA local UPF and Edge Computing servers at the Iasi 5G Lab data center, providing low-latency video analytics. This architecture also includes a dedicated URLLC slice ensuring prioritized latency of around 8 ms, crucial for real-time applications. The successful activation of 5G SA and NSA hybrid mode and initial field tests in the Iasi area confirm the system's ability to handle real-time traffic, with high uplink and downlink performances. In this context, the experimental facilities located in Belgium (comprising several testbeds as small-scale experimental sites located in Antwerp and Ghent) were used as a complementary setup to the trial site in the Romanian cluster, in particular to perform pre-trial research and development activities related to UC4.

The **Greek cluster** provided an experimental private network infrastructure based on 3GPP Rel-15 NSA architecture to perform the tests and evaluate the performances of the application related to the use cases which on field trials took place at the Athens International Airport (AIA), in the Municipality of Athens (Technopolis area), and at the Corinth Canal Museum. As per the Turin site of the Italian cluster, the trials have been performed over the available commercial network to exploit its broad coverage and stable performance to validate the different use cases under real-world conditions.

Besides the core project's activities described above, through the interaction with WP7, WP2 has also supported the onboarding and integration of the Open Call sub-projects, which either exploited or extended the existing project's infrastructures through the introduction of 24 new use cases (one per sub-project). Concerning the Option 1a and Option 1b sub-projects, as reported in the specific sections of this deliverable, the performed trials further validated the openness, adaptability, and modularity of the TrialsNet architecture, enabling new verticals and enhancements of the existing use cases. At the same time, in relation to the Option 2 sub-projects, these contributed to the extension of the project's clusters (and sites) with 8 new locations as well as 7 additional network infrastructures (i.e., private and experimental) with various types of deployment and coverage.

This deliverable also provides the final implementation of the TrialsNet's Vertical and Horizontal innovations as well as the sustainability solutions that have been studied and introduced by WP2. While, on one side, the proposed innovations contribute to the infrastructure's flexibility and capacity for scaling with new applications and features, on the other side, the sustainability solutions are going to be crucial for the success of future experiments and contribute to the long-term viability of the network. Besides the final development, the project also identified specific KPIs for each of the introduced solutions which measurements have been collected (both through simulations or real setups, depending on the context) and properly analyzed to validate their effectiveness.

Finally, the deliverable reports about the contribution to the standard provided by TrialsNet in the context of 3GPP activities towards the 6G definition. In particular, TIM, UC3M, and IMEC jointly collaborated to elaborate an input with the aim to emphasize the need for a sustainable achievement of relevant KPIs (which has been identified through the project's trial activities) and proposing the Zero-touch Service Management (ZSM) framework as an enabler for achieving these. To further strength the impact and create synergies, TrialsNet also initiated a collaboration with the project ORIGAMI which help to a workshop in which common strategies and fay forward to contribute to the standard were finalized. As a result, TIM presented on behalf of TrialsNet a contribution to the 3GPP workshop on 6G held the 10-11th of March 2025 in Incheon aiming at identifying the main topics to be addressed in the definition of 6G by proposing integrated, scalable, and autonomous solutions for future mobile infrastructures.

1 Introduction

In the context of TrialsNet, Work Package 2 (WP2) played a central role in the design, integration, and deployment of advanced network and platform solutions that support the execution of the project's large-scale trials. These solutions aim to address the technical requirements of the diverse use cases explored across the project, while validating the capabilities and limitations of 5G and Beyond 5G (B5G) technologies in realistic scenarios. Deliverable D2.4, provides a comprehensive overview of the final deployment status and integration outcomes achieved by WP2, building upon the intermediate results documented in the previous deliverables D2.2 [1] and D2.3 [2]. It also incorporates additional developments carried out by the Open Call sub-projects and reflects the lessons learned from the trials conducted across all geographical clusters.

The document is structured as follows:

Section 2 presents the final infrastructure deployed in each cluster, highlighting the specific configurations and adaptations for each use case.

Section 3 focuses on the extensions enabled through the Open Call sub-projects and their technical integration with the existing platforms.

Sections 4 and 5 report the finalized implementation and validation of the key innovations and sustainability aspects developed within WP2.

Section 6 identifies the emerging standardization opportunities based on the insights gained throughout the trials.

Finally, Section 7 summarizes the main conclusions and outlines future directions for platform and network evolution within TrialsNet.

2 Final TrialsNet clusters' infrastructures

In this Section, all the final deployment activities carried out in the different TrialsNet clusters are discussed, highlighting the main achievements and the necessary actions for the trials execution, for both the internal ones and the ones coming from the sub-projects. All the descriptions of the use cases will be provided in the forthcoming WP3, 4, and 5 deliverables.

2.1 Italian cluster (Turin site)

This section describes the final network solutions for the platform of the Turin site, part of the Italian cluster in which the trials of UC5 “Control Room in Metaverse”, UC12 “City Parks in Metaverse” and UC13 “Extended Reality (XR) Museum Experience” has been performed. In addition, the Open Call sub-projects “Dreampark” by AnotherReality has been implemented as an Option 1b of UC12.

As already described in D2.3 [2] the Turin site in the Italian cluster is based on wide network 5G coverage, based on the TIM commercial network, and includes a set of technologies developed in previous EU founded projects, and others hardware/software components such as OpenStack cloud and XR platform.

2.1.1 Final deployment

The final Turin site infrastructure has been deployed with no changes since D2.3 [2]. The wide coverage guaranteed by TIM commercial network (Rel. 15) has been used for Outdoor and indoor UC execution with good performance. Figure 1 shows the trials locations, spread above the Turin downtown area, including several indoor locations (using macro cell coverage) and an extended outdoor area (Parco Del Valentino, approximate area 0,5 km²) mostly covered by two macro sites. Open Call sub-project didn't require any network upgrade, since the usage of commercial network and self-provided cloud hosting.

Figure 1. Torino site UCs locations.

2.1.2 Performed trials

This section provides an overview of the Turin cluster UCs trials, where the commercial network has been used to provide the required large-scale coverage. Details on the use cases performed activities, including trials results, will be provided in the final D3.3, D4.3, and D5.3 deliverables.

The trial of UC5 “Control Room in Metaverse” was successfully held on 15 October 2024. This involved 18 agents from safety and security forces of the Turin municipality. This use case simulated a serious accident involving two injured people at the Parc of Valentino, already described in D2.3 [2].

The trial of UC12 “City Parks in Metaverse” was held on 14 and 15 November at the Parco del Valentino and the nearby Talent Garden building in Turin. It involved 130 students and 6 professors from the secondary school “Liceo Artistico Cottini” in Turin and 15 staff from the TrialsNet partners, already described in D2.3 [2].

The trial of UC13 “Extended Reality (XR) Museum Experience” has been held in four different museums. The one performed at Palazzo Madama on 13/3/2025 involved 46 students aged 15-16, 2 teachers and a museum guide while the other performed at GAM (Galleria Arte Moderna) on 17/3/2025 involved 34 students aged 15-16, two teachers and a museum guide. The devices used in the 2 trials were the following:

- 13 tablets (Samsung and Lenovo),
- 12 VR headset Meta Quest 2),
- 2 CPEs (ZTE)
- Laptops (Lenovo, MAC)

The trial was successful as shown by the high level of user appreciation at 80% on average. No major problems were detected at the level of the 5G connection. Some errors detected in the package transmission did not affect the experience. This was confirmed by the analysis of the correlation between KPIs and KVI which revealed no significant relationship.

The trial performed on Museo del Risorgimento on the 17/3/2025 involved 114 people in total of which 40 high-school students (15 to 17 years old) from 2 different schools and 3 teachers as well as 71 tourists (from the museum’s visitors) and museum guides. The following devices were used:

- 8 Meta Quest 2 VR Headsets (for the VR museum experience) including 4 spares for recharge, connected via Wi-Fi to 2 5G CPE router
- 2 5G ZTE CPE in the Sala Plebisciti of the museum

The trial performed on Museo Pietro Micca on the 24/3/2025 involved 41 people in total of which 35 high-school students (15 to 17 years old) from 2 different schools and 2 teachers as well as museum guides. The following devices were used:

- 6 Meta Quest 2 VR Headsets (for the VR museum experience) including 3 spares for recharge, connected via Wi-Fi to 2 5G CPE router
- 2 5G ZTE CPE at the ground floor of the museum

All the trials were concluded successfully, meeting the expected KPIs and KVIs. On the KPIs side, the infrastructure of the Turin site (encompassing the commercial 5G network coverage) effectively supported the trials’ setup and execution. Overall, the KVIs have been evaluated through 193 valid questionnaires collected from the four museums. The results indicate that the target of 70% appreciation was achieved across all KVIs. Additionally, the percentage of participants with an average KVI score above 3 ranged over 80%, except for the "intention to buy" that can likely be attributed to the young age of most of the participants, who were students between 15 and 18 years old with limited spending capability.

Finally, the Open Cal “Dreampark” sub-project performed four trials hosted at LINKS foundation facility and the Talent Garden. The following devices were used:

- 5G router with TIM sim card
- PC/Laptop gaming workstations
- VR Headsets (10 samples, mainly meta quest 3, and some quest 2)

2.2 Italian cluster (Pisa site)

The following subsections describe the final deployment and architecture of the network infrastructure in Pisa that is used to carry out the use cases UC7 "Remote Proctoring", UC8 "Smart Ambulance", UC9 "Adaptive Control of Hannes prosthesis", and open call's COMO5 "Continuous monitoring of patients with chronic diseases via 5G".

The scheme in Figure 2 highlights the main connectivity-related systems involved in supporting the mentioned use cases, all experimented at the CNR Campus premises in Pisa. The scheme is an exemplification of the detailed orientation map reported in Section 2.2.1 of D2.3 [2].

In the final implementation, all the devices (e.g. XR glasses, eco-scan...) are connected to the 5G network using CPEs which, in turn, are connected to indoor and outdoor antennas. Signals from the antennas are routed to a baseband unit system, which handles the initial stages of signal processing. The ER Innovative Orchestrator, a software platform enhanced with artificial intelligence to dynamically manage and optimize the flow of data, interacts with the radio and transport infrastructure.

The transport layer, supported by high-capacity Ericsson's Router 6000 devices, connects to both a User Plane Function (UPF) module and a gateway. The UPF is a fundamental component of 5G architecture, tasked with forwarding user data and enabling local breakout to reduce latency. From the CNR Campus, the network extends toward two remote destinations: the Hospital in Massa and the TIM Site in Turin. Connectivity to the hospital is established via a dedicated gateway and is made possible over a high-speed DWDM link. Simultaneously, the system connects to the TIM Site in Turin, which hosts the core 5G Packet Core and the Unified Data Management (UDM) system. These components handle subscriber authentication, session management, and ensure the overall integrity and efficiency of the network. A gateway at the TIM Site manages the interface between the external emergency healthcare data and the internal telecom infrastructure.

Figure 2. High level network architecture for the Pisa site.

2.2.1 Final deployment

The final deployment of the network scheme for the Pisa site is reported in Figure 3. The network comprises two routers R6675: one dedicated to the core network and another dedicated to the RAN. Several servers are connected to the core router, each associated with an implemented use case. The AX73 router/modem provides Internet connectivity for management operations. A server running the ER Innovative Orchestrator [1] is connected to perform dynamic configuration of service requests, dynamic association between 5G QoS Identifiers (5QIs) and International Mobile Subscriber Identities (IMSIs), and QoS settings in the transport network. The CNR network connects the routers to the CN TLAB TIM network in Turin, and an IPsec tunnel secures communication between the core router and this network. The two routers are interconnected via two links labelled as 1/15 and 1/7 in figure. Link 1/15 has been designated for high-priority traffic. The gNodeB (5G base station) is connected to the RAN router, providing 5G connectivity to both the indoor room and the outdoor environment. The radio system support 3GPP Rel-16 and, in the trial, it uses the mmWave band SA Rel-16, at 26 GHz on mmW spectrum (26.9-27.1 GHz, 200 MHz) [1].

Figure 3. High level network scheme for the Pisa site.

An Ericsson AIR 1281 antenna, illustrated in Figure 4 (a), is installed at the indoor CNR room designated for the UC7, UC8, UC9, and COMO5 test activities. Meanwhile, a second Ericsson AIR 1281 antenna, as in Figure 4 (b), is set up outdoors, facing the parking area where the UC8 experiments are scheduled to take place.

Additionally, the rack reported in Figure 4 (c) is posed in the CNR server room, located near the previously mentioned indoor area, to house the Ericsson Baseband Unit BB6651, which supports the chosen mmWave bands. The rack also hosts the Ericsson Router 6000 used to connect the site with both Turin (where the core network is located) and Massa Hospital (remote site for UC7 and UC8).

The two antennas are situated within the same building as the server room to reduce the need for extensive cabling. Additionally, the rack includes systems that facilitate a VPN connection to the TIM site in Turin and a fiber optic connection to the hospital in Massa. Performance testing at the user equipment level will commence once the Customer Premises Equipment (CPE) is activated and connected to the terminals and devices.

Figure 4. (a) Indoor antenna, (b) outdoor antenna, (c) rack with baseband and routers.

As introduced above, the set-up of the network infrastructure includes also the ER Innovative Orchestrator developed in the project. Such ER Innovative Orchestrator receives dynamically the request of each service (e.g., the implemented UCs) with specific KPI for geographical area and configures dynamically the network accordingly. All details related to the ER Innovative Orchestrator are reported in Section 4.2.2.

Tests related to the performance of the infrastructure (throughput and latency) and tests related to the ER Innovative Orchestrator have been done. In this section the test on throughput and latency of the E2E network infrastructure (i.e. including mobile and transport networks) are reported. The aim was to assess the network's ability to handle high-bandwidth applications and real-time operations (latency critical).

As input, iperf traffic was generated by two PCs: one connected to the antenna (either indoor or outdoor), acting as the iperf client, and the other as the iperf server. Bandwidth tests were conducted using the iperf traffic generator with multiple simultaneous streams in both TCP and UDP modes to saturate the available bandwidth.

In the *indoor* environment, TCP tests achieved a downlink throughput of 850 Mbit/s and an uplink throughput of 200 Mbit/s. UDP tests resulted in 800 Mbit/s downlink and 120 Mbit/s uplink, both with packet loss below 0.1%. Latency, measured via ping under both loaded and unloaded conditions, ranged from 6 to 12 milliseconds.

For the *outdoor* tests, similar measurements were conducted at three different locations, represented as green, blue, and black spots in Figure 5. These locations were chosen based on the coverage range of the external antenna. Performance in the best-covered areas (black and blue spots) was comparable to the indoor results, while the location with the weakest signal (green spot) exhibited reduced throughput and increased latency. The overall coverage area defined by the antenna's usable range was approximately 7,400 m², equivalent to about 0.0074 km².

Figure 5. Outdoor coverage and test points for the Pisa site.

A summary of indoor and outdoor tests collected in April 2025, reporting bandwidth and latency measurements is detailed in Figure 6. Values reported in Figure 6 can be compared with the measurable indicators (KPIs) defined in document D4.1 [16]. Specifically, KPI#03 (throughput performance) and KPI#09 (latency) are the primary focus, as detailed below.

The measured throughput performance (KPI#03) exceeds the requirements for all use cases. Validation efforts concentrated on downlink (DL) aggregate throughput, with the highest requirement being 150 Mbit/s for COMO5. Other requirements include 25 Mbit/s for UC7/UC8 and 90 Mbit/s for UC9. Field tests demonstrated significantly higher performance, achieving downlink speeds of 850 Mbps indoors and 850–900 Mbps outdoors. In addition, substantial uplink (UL) throughput was recorded, with indoor uplink speeds reaching 200 Mbps and outdoor speeds ranging from 150 to 200 Mbps.

Application latency requirements (KPI#09) are also fully met. Maximum one-way latency is specified as 50 ms for UC7/UC8 and a more stringent 10 ms for UC9. Field measurements captured round-trip latency, which ranged from 6–12 ms (indoor, UC7/UC9) to 5–15 ms (outdoor, UC8). Since one-way latency is approximately half the round-trip value, the effective one-way latency is about 2.5 to 7.5 ms. This result is well within the strict 10 ms limit required for UC9 and is significantly better than the 50 ms threshold for UC7 and UC8, thereby confirming full compliance with the latency KPIs.

Bandwidth (iperf traffic)					
Environment	Protocol	Spot	Download (DL)	Upload (UL)	Notes
Outdoor	TCP	Black Spot	900 Mbit/s	200 Mbit/s	
		Blue Spot	850 Mbit/s	150 Mbit/s	
		Green Spot	300–400 Mbit/s	20–30 Mbit/s	
	UDP*	Black Spot	800 Mbit/s	200 Mbit/s	Packet loss < 0.1%
		Blue Spot	700 Mbit/s	150 Mbit/s	Packet loss < 0.1%
		Green Spot	300–400 Mbit/s	20 Mbit/s	Packet loss < 0.1%
Indoor	TCP	—	850 Mbit/s	200 Mbit/s	Multiple streams used
	UDP*	—	800 Mbit/s	120 Mbit/s	Packet loss < 0.1%

* UDP values measured with < 0.1% packet loss

Latency (ping)		
Environment	Spot	Latency
Outdoor	Black Spot	5–15 ms
	Blue Spot	5–15 ms
	Green Spot	10–20 ms
Indoor	—	6–12 ms

Figure 6. Indoor and outdoor measurements.

What reported is a validation related to transmission and network aspects. It is crucial that the required performance for each use case is ensured under the network's operating conditions, for example by guaranteeing the downlink and latency requirements for the smart ambulance. In this context, the ER Innovative Orchestrator operates to ensure the necessary service levels, as explained in Section 4.2.2.

2.2.2 Performed trials

From May 2025 on, all the use cases associated with Pisa Cluster, including COMO 5 from open calls, have been deployed in field and tested at various levels. Pictures are reported in Figure 7 referring to moments of the experimentation. An overview of the performed trials is reported in the following while further details focused on the user experience will be reported in the final deliverable D4.3 of WP4.

Figure 7. Pictures of the on-field trials in Pisa cluster.

Regarding UC7, an initial trial session was conducted on July 7th, 2025, connecting a surgeon located at the CNR in Pisa with another surgeon performing an angiography at the hospital in Massa. The test lasted about two hours, with one hour dedicated to tuning and setting up the AR devices (Rods&Cones) used by the surgeon in Massa during the procedure. Additional trial sessions are being scheduled according to the hospital's availability. However, the first session has already demonstrated outstanding results in terms of quality of experience for both doctors connected remotely.

A UC8 trial was conducted on June 27th, 2025. The trial was carried out with the kind collaboration of the Pubblica Assistenza di Pisa (a non-profit organization that provides emergency transport in the city), which provided an ambulance with three paramedics on board. With the help of a volunteer, a simulated medical emergency was staged, and the volunteer was subsequently brought aboard the ambulance. A sufficiently large outdoor area of the CNR Campus (directly covered by the TrialsNet 5G outdoor antenna) allowed the ambulance to move around and thus test onboard services in a real mobility scenario. Both the portable echocardiography system and AR/VR devices with gesture technology for advanced telepresence (all connected with a 5G CPE) were tested. The network fully supported the expected service level, providing both the ambulance staff and the remote personnel (connected from Massa Hospital) with a quality of experience deemed suitable for the use case. Additionally, a representative of the COMO5 open call use case was present with its equipment to conduct tests on board the ambulance. Further details regarding the specific tests carried out for COMO5 are provided below. The simultaneous testing of UC8 and COMO5 was also significant in terms of the ER Innovative Orchestrator's ability to manage multiple services concurrently, as explained in Section 4.2.2.

For UC9, pre-trials were also conducted in the area covered by the indoor antenna. The prosthesis was connected to the remote server in two different ways: via cable and via 5G network. The differences between the two options were assessed using volunteers. Since there are currently no dongles available on the market that work on mmWave of a 5G SA antenna, the prosthesis has been connected to the 5G CPE via an ethernet cable.

As part of the pre-trial activities, a series of tests were conducted to validate the integration and performance of the Open Call sub-project COMO5 platform with the ER Innovative Orchestrator (see also Section 4.2.2) in a realistic environment at the CNR Pisa site. These tests aimed to verify the correct prioritization of patient-critical traffic over background traffic using a private indoor 5G network. Two COMO5 team members simulated a patient and a clinician. The patient's kit was connected via Wi-Fi hot spot to the 5G network via CPE1, while CPE2 generated controlled UDP disturbance traffic (150 Mbit/s). To further stress the uplink, an additional 150 Mbit/s of traffic was generated from CPE1, intentionally exceeding the network's uplink capacity (200 Mbit/s).

Figure 8. COMO5 network infrastructure.

During the test, the patient's kit was set to continuously upload data, simulating a critical (CODE RED) condition. The clinician manually changed the patient status from "deteriorating" to "stable" after three minutes. These status changes triggered the ER Innovative Orchestrator to adjust the QoS (5QI), giving higher priority to traffic from CPE1 when the patient was critical. Results indicate that prioritization via the ER Innovative Orchestrator ensured consistent throughput and low latency for critical traffic despite background interference. Once the priority was removed, the patient's data experienced severe degradation, including zero throughput intervals and significantly increased application RTT (in the order of seconds), potentially compromising application responsiveness. As mentioned above, additional simultaneous tests of UC8 and COMO5 were performed on board of the smart ambulance on July 27th.

2.3 Spanish cluster

The following sub-sections describe the final deployment and architecture of the infrastructure located in Madrid that was employed to perform UC1 “Smart Crowd Monitoring”, UC6 “Mass Casualty Incident” and UC10 “Immersive Fan Engagement” trials, and to host the open call sub-projects Option1a specific of this cluster.

The final network solution was based on a 5G Stand-Alone (SA) FR2 non-public-network (meaning that only high band or also called millimeter wave frequencies were used in the RAN domain, without the need to have another layer for anchor and control-plane purposes). This final configuration had as main change the new prototype Customer Premises Equipment’s (CPEs) that are based on Qualcomm’s SDX75 chipset and required several configurations to connect to 5G FR2 SA network, as explained in the deliverable D2.3 [2] The FR2 band used for the mmWave deployment was n258, with 800 MHz of aggregated bandwidth available for downlink (DL) and 400 MHz of aggregated bandwidth granted for uplink (UL). The spectrum allocation being utilized is part of the licensed frequencies in band n258 assigned to Telefónica for its commercial network operations [1]. The network deployed consisted of three sectors to provide the 5G SA FR2 coverage in the Movistar Arena venue, where the use cases were successfully validated during last Sunday 16th March 2025 [3].

In terms of the Open Call related sub-projects, two proposals leveraging the Spanish cluster are an Option 1a:

- **Sub-project “Remote Coordination”**: the proposal used up to 10 UEs (both smartphones and tablet), which had midband n78 NR SA capabilities.
- **Sub-project “Skylink Vision”**: similar as the other proposal two CPEs supporting midband n78 NR SA band were used.

Therefore, since both Open Call trials required NR SA mid-band coverage in band n78, trials were carried out in 5Tonic laboratory [4] premises, within IMDEA Networks institute [5] where Ericsson have permanent NR mid-band coverage (n78 band) from one outdoor and two indoor 5G mid-band radio solutions.

2.3.1 Final deployment

Final deployment of the network infrastructure for the trials in the Spanish cluster can be divided into two sub-sections. Firstly, the section describes the set-up for the main use cases performed at Movistar Arena, followed by the architecture deployed at 5Tonic laboratory where the Open Call sub-projects took place.

2.3.1.1 Infrastructure deployment at Movistar Arena

Deliverable D2.3 [2] described the final infrastructure upgrade (both in terms of hardware (HW), with new CPEs, and software (SW), with a new upgrade package in the gNB, followed by new configurations and functionalities) that was done to have a Rel-17 NR SA mmWave non-public-network available for the trials.

So-called “Penguin”, the flight rack that was placed in Movistar Arena’s data center (Figure 9), and it is composed by a Router 6675 [7] acting as traffic aggregator for the Baseband 6648 [7] with the gNB functionalities and RAN signaling processing and the Local Packet Gateway (LPG) [8] providing on the edge the 5G Core User Plane Function (UPF) and managing data traffic within the private network itself, with clear advantages in security, privacy and latency. Moreover, the flight rack also has an Ubuntu based applications server.

Figure 9. NR SA FR2 non-public-network flight rack (“Penguin”) at Movistar Arena venue (Madrid).

The existing 5G Core infrastructure at 5Tonic laboratory, with the rest of control-plane functions was connected to the flight rack by using a Virtual Private Network (VPN) based on OpenVPN and Tailscale commercial solutions (in redundant mode, with OpenVPN working as main solution, and the other as backup). All traffic going outside the flight rack was routed via the VPN from the applications server where they were installed. The internet connectivity, for the VPN establishment, was provided by a commercial fiber connection from Movistar (Telefonica commercial brand), with a router that located in the data center and had one free ethernet port (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Telefonica's commercial router for fiber optic connection.

To ensure precise time and phase synchronization for the NR FR2 Time Division Duplexing (TDD) cells, the existing Global Positioning System (GPS) active antenna and GNSS Receiver Unit (GRU) module, previously deployed by Telefonica and Ericsson for Movistar Arena's commercial 5G network, was utilized.

On February 3rd 2025, the whole Trialsnet spanish cluster partners from UC1, UC6 and UC10 had a final site survey at Movistar Arena in Madrid [10] (former Wizink Center) to verify all installation details for the radio access network, specially the distribution for the fibers towards the mmWave antennas (Common Public Radio Interface (CPRI) links) and needs for the different use cases (such as ethernet cables, WiFi access points, electricity outlets and miscelanous furnitures).

To develop later on the 5G infrastructure details for the trials in Movistar Arena venue, the following Figure 11 highlights graphically the overall network diagram of the infrastructure. For UC10, two sectors providing 5G SA FR2 coverage were deployed, meanwhile for UC1 and UC6, one sector was installed. All of them using the Ericsson AIR 5322, part of the Ericsson Radio System portfolio, supporting n258 for 5G mmW spectrum [11].

Figure 11. Network diagram in Movistar Arena venue and 5Tonic laboratory for UC1, UC6 and UC10.

In the following Figure 12, it is displayed a printout from the gNB where can be seen the final connection set-up, with the three AIR 5322 sectors and all of them with CPRI links of around 300 meters of single-mode fiber between the baseband and the antennas. The fiber was deployed at Movistar Arena specifically and dedicated for the trial but was reusing part of the dark fiber that Ericsson deployed for Telefonica's commercial network in the facilities. By using dual-fiber 25 Gbps SFP28 modules, only two CPRI per sector were needed to achieve the maximum throughput and performance of the network, making the installation easier, considering that was a temporary installation.

Figure 12. Printout of the gNB with 3 sectors CPRIs.

More in detail, Figure 13 and Figure 14 depict the high-level network architecture diagrams for UC10 as well as UC1 and UC6 respectively.

Figure 13. UC10 high-level network architecture diagram.

Figure 14. UC1 and UC6 high-level network architecture diagram.

For a coherent understanding, the infrastructure is detailed in the following sub-sections per each radio sector, i.e. coverage area.

Sector 1 (UC10 “Immersive Fan Engagement”)

This 5G antenna was installed in the upper grandstands heading to the basketball court (that have an approximate dimension of 92x50 m and 4600 m²) and it was providing 5G coverage to the entire court area where three mmWave SA CPEs were deployed which by ethernet cable assured connectivity to two 180° cameras located in each basket (CPE1 and CPE2) and to one 360° camera (CPE3) located in one of the corners of the court (Figure 15). This sector was carrying mainly uplink video traffic from YBVR cameras for UC10. The following Figure 15 and Figure 16 show the final location of the HW infrastructure for Sector 1 inside Movistar Arena.

Figure 15. 5G CPE1, CPE2 and CPE3 location within the basketball court.

Figure 16. AIR 5322 n258 (Sector 1).

In the following Figure 17, the performance of the 5G SA mmW network are reported, being measured with iPerf3 towards the flight rack applications server. Sustained 390 Mbits/sec for UL were available for the three mentioned cameras. Regarding DL, around 3.2 Gbits/sec throughput results were achieved on the court zone. Those results were close to the ones obtained during the configuration in 5Tonic laboratory as described in the deliverable D2.3[1]. The configuration was kept as in the laboratory during the pre-trials, having 8 Component Carrier (CC) in downlink (for a total bandwidth of 800 MHz) and 4CC in uplink (for a total bandwidth of 400 MHz), the highest modulation supported for DL was 256QAM, meanwhile for UL was 64 QAM. Regarding TDD pattern, it was configured on all 5G cells, a DDDSU structure, being “D” a downlink frame, “S” a special slot frame and “U”, an uplink frame. The Special slot “S” format was set with a ratio of 10 downlinks, a 2-symbol guard period and 2 uplinks (10:2:2). CPE orientation and AIR 5322 mechanical down-tilt was optimized during the installation on the same day of the trial.

Figure 17. iPerf3 performance of the 5G SA mmW in Movistar Arena (DL and UL).

Sector 2 (UC10 “Immersive Fan Engagement”)

This second 5G sector was installed in the backstage corridors of the venue, where YBVR installed their production set for video/images control. The coverage area to cover with this 5G mmW antenna was only the room, so the AIR was configured to the minimum radiation power, complying with Electromagnetic Field (EMF) exposure and local authority regulations. In terms of radio configuration, this sector had exactly the same settings as the 1st one and in terms of performance similar results were obtained for DL/UL traffic.

YBVR defined two scenarios to test the 5G network. “In-venue” scenario with mobile smartphones, where the user is receiving multi-screen information on the mobile smartphone showing the different TV feeds and choosing the preferred feed at any time. The second scenario is “at-home” where users can watch the event anywhere through mobile devices and VR headsets thanks to the cameras positioned on the courtside of the match, providing a seamless viewing perspective [13][14].

The 4th CPE (Figure 18) was installed in this room to provide 5G connectivity to the production set and also via an ethernet cable from the CPE4 to a Wi-Fi access point located in the “in-venue” area that was providing the immersive video experience to commercial smartphones for the end-users. Wi-Fi connectivity was needed on the mentioned area, as currently there are no available 5G SA mmW smartphones on the market.

Therefore, this sector was carrying mainly downlink video traffic coming from YBVR cameras located in the court (Sector 1) for UC10. But also, it was carrying some uplink video traffic that was sent to the cloud and broadcasted to “at-home” experience area with the VR headsets.

Following Figure 18 and Figure 19 present the network deployment for the Sector 2.

Figure 18. AIR 5322 n258 and CPE4 location within production set room (Sector 2).

Figure 19. Video feed coming from court cameras to production set and “in-venue” experience areas.

The “At-home” experience area was out of the scope of Ericsson deployment as the VR headsets were connected via a Wi-Fi access point, provided by YBVR, that was routed to internet by an external network. This traffic was out of Ericsson non-public network deployed on Movistar Arena.

Sector 3 (UC1 “Smart Crowd Monitoring” and UC6 “Mass Casualty Incident”)

The third 5G sector was located in the main entrance (located in Goya Street) of Movistar Arena venue and was intended to provide 5G SA mmW coverage to UC1 and UC6 in an area of approximately 45 x 10 m (450 m²). CPE1 and CPE2 that were re-used from the UC10, as both use cases happened at different moments of the trial day, were served by sector three 5G coverage.

No particularities can be derived from the Sector 3 compared to the others, in terms of radio configuration and performance. Following Figure 20 shows the location of the 5G antenna installed for UC1 and UC6 trials.

Figure 20. AIR 5322 n258 (Sector 3).

The CPE1 (Figure 21) was installed on the 3rd floor of Goya access, where Prosegur Security installed their control room (called iSOC) and was connected through an ethernet cable to the CPE1. This CPE1 was from one hand, processing DL signaling, video traffic and area mapping coming from the devices used in the UC1, but on the other hand was sending UL video traffic to Prosegur’s cloud platform (called Nimbus) and UL signaling to the devices for their remote control and configuration.

Figure 21. CPE1 and Prosegur's iSOC location in Movistar Arena venue.

The second CPE2 (Figure 22) was installed on the first floor of Goya access, where Hikvision surveillance cameras [15] and Lidar UC1 devices were directly connected by ethernet cable to the CPE2 (Figure 22). A Wi-Fi access point was also connected to this CPE2 to provide connectivity to three different robots that were moving on the ground floor after the security access control, such as Yellow or Kiir0 (Figure 23).

All the UC1 devices connected to CPE2 were producing mostly uplink data flows sent to the iSOC (control room), so the traffic in this sector was most of the time symmetrical (in terms of DL and UL), as described in Deliverable 2.3 [2].

Figure 22. CPE2 and Prosegur's Lidar and Cameras.

Figure 23. Prosegur's robots: Yellow and Kiir0.

Also, the mentioned Wi-Fi access point provided internet access to the wearables that were distributed during the trial for UC6 (see Figure 24), and they were sending all the vital signs to the WINGS server (C6 server) located in Greece.

Figure 24. Wearable devices for UC6.

2.3.1.2 Integration of the Open Call sub-projects (Option 1)

As explained in the introduction of the Spanish cluster, two Open Call sub-projects were trialed, for which Ericsson provided the NR SA mid-band (n78) coverage in 5Tonic laboratory inside IMDEA Networks premises. The Open Call sub-project “Remote Coordination” used the smartphones compatible with NR SA n78 band listed in Table 1.

Table 1. NR SA n78 smartphones used during "Remote Coordination" trial.

Terminal Type	Name
UE	1x Nokia XR21
UE	1x Nokia Shadow/G42 5G
UE	3x Crosscall CoreZ5
UE	1x i.Safe IS540.2
Tablet	1x i.Safe IS940.2

The UEs had installed the “Lifelink MCx Connect” Eviden application, for Mission Critical (MCx) private and group calls and were used by Madrid’s regional firefighters, meanwhile the tablet was running the “Dispatcher MCx” client, acting as a remote center coordinator. The interaction of the 5G SA terminals with Ericsson network can be seen in Figure 25.

Figure 25. Eviden architecture interworking with Ericsson 5G SA network.

The second Open Call sub-project “SkyLink Vision” used the Ericsson provided WNC CPE compatible with NR SA n78 band as shown in Figure 26.

Figure 26. WNC 5G SA mid-band (n78) CPE.

The high-level architecture and interaction of SkyLink Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) and Ground Control station components with Ericsson 5G network can be seen in the following Figure 27.

Figure 27. “SkyLink Vision” high-level architecture.

For the trial, a single CPE was providing 5G mid-band coverage to both main components all connected through a Raspberry Pi 4 [18]. The ground control station used to simulate the remote control towards the UAV autopilot and the high-resolution camera for ground images are reported in Figure 28. Another generic computer was used for the cloud server, where video / localization services could be accessed (Figure 29) and to manage through graphical interfaces the different components.

Figure 28. “Sky Link Vision” components.

Figure 29. "Sky Link Vision" cloud server.

Due to the needs of “Remote Coordination” and “Sky Link” Open Call sub-projects, the areas involved in the trial were 5Tonic laboratory and the basketball court behind, as shown in Figure 30 [17].

Figure 30. IMDEA Networks and 5Tonic Lab premises.

On those areas, Ericsson have permanent 5G SA coverage in mid-band (n78 band), using up to 100 MHz (DL and UL) of licensed Telefónica’s commercial spectrum. So-called “Flamingo”, the flight rack that Ericsson has permanent in 5Tonic lab can be seen in Figure 31.

Figure 31. NR SA Mid-band non-public-network flight rack (“Flamingo”) at 5Tonic (IMDEA Networks).

The HW components of the flight rack are the same as the ones described for the mmWave NPN “Penguin”, varying only in the Ericsson Radio System used. This flight rack is also connected to the 5G Core infrastructure at 5Tonic laboratory (Figure 32), but in this case no VPN is needed, since both domains are in the same premises.

Figure 32. 5G Core infrastructure at 5Tonic Laboratory.

To provide 5G SA mid-band coverage, “Flamingo” has been integrated with two radio solutions. Inside the laboratory room, the mid-band coverage in band n78 is provided by one 4TX/4RX micro Radio 4408 and the passive antenna 6524 and the Ericsson Radio Dot system [2], based on an Indoor Radio Unit 8846 [3], that aggregates RF signals and provides power to the Radio Dot 4479. The HW setup is depicted in Figure 33.

Figure 33. 5Tonic laboratory - Indoor 5G SA mid-band solution.

The other radio solution was intended to provide outdoor mid-band coverage in the basketball court area, and for that purpose, Ericsson deployed one 4TX/4RX micro Radio 4408 and the passive antenna 6524 as can be seen in Figure 34.

Figure 34. 5Tonic laboratory - Outdoor 5G SA mid-band solution.

For that purpose, coverage, data session continuity and user experience tests (with Skype videocalls) were done during February 2025 with both indoor and outdoor Radio 4408 on-air and performing handover between both cells, but also with only having on-air indoor Radio 4408.

Those tests concluded that tuning the radiated power, indoor Radio 4408 was serving both areas with good signal strength values and user experience. For the trial, 100 MHz of BW was configured on the 5G cell, and modulation was kept both in DL and UL to 64QAM, making the channel transmissions more robust, as the traffic demand for the trial was not close to the theoretical capacity of the 5G cell.

2.3.2 Performed trials

For the Spanish cluster, all the trials were conducted, as described in previous section, and summarized here:

- UC1, UC6 and UC10 were trialed during two basketball matches at Movistar Arena on Sunday 16th March 2025
- Sub-project “Remote Coordination” was trialed on Monday 17th March 2025 at IMDEA Networks institute where 5Tonic laboratory is located
- Sub-project “Skylink Vision” was trialed on Wednesday 2nd April 2025 at IMDEA Networks institute where 5Tonic laboratory is located

For “Remote Coordination” Open Call sub-project trial was conducted both indoors in 5Tonic laboratory and outdoors in the basketball court (Figure 35), so 5G connectivity was needed in both areas.

Figure 35. "Remote Coordination" Open Call sub-project trial execution (17th March 2025).

For “SkyLink Vision” Open Call sub-project, trial was conducted only indoors in 5Tonic laboratory (Figure 36), so 5G connectivity was in this case provided by the Radio Dot 4479. 5G cell configuration was the same as in the 1st sub-project, as neither here the required network KPIs were specially demanding.

Figure 36. "SkyLink Vision" Open Call sub-project trial execution (2nd April 2025).

During all the trials, Ericsson stored the following network KPIs: Downlink throughput per user (KPI#01), Downlink throughput per user (KPI#02), Downlink aggregate throughput (KPI#03), Uplink aggregate throughput (#04), Application round-trip latency (KPI#08) and Service availability (KPI#17) reported in Figure 42.

During the validation process of Ericsson internal monitoring tool, referred to as probe, a specific limitation was identified when deploying it on Qualcomm mmW CPEs based on the aarch64 architecture and running OpenWrt 22.03.5 [19]. This probe is designed to capture network KPIs directly from a network interface and is deployed in Linux environments on x86_64 architecture. For CPEs, a specific version was compiled, adapted to the aarch64 GNU/Linux architecture. During initial testing at 5Tonic laboratory using iperf3 from the CPEs themselves, the probes correctly recorded the traffic. However, when the traffic was generated by devices connected to the CPEs, with the latter acting as routers, the tool showed no activity, as it was happening in the UC1, UC6 and UC10 trials. Upon detailed analysis, it was determined that the CPEs utilized Qualcomm's IPA (IP Accelerator) technology, which enables packet forwarding without involving the main processor, redirecting flows directly between network interfaces using specialized hardware. As a result, the traffic does not reach the CPU, preventing its observation by both our probe and traditional tools such as tcpdump, a command line utility that allows to capture and analyze network traffic, which also rely on user-plane traffic visibility for packet capture.

The “Remote Coordination” Open Call sub-project trial that was using proprietary devices, such as smartphones or tablets, had neither possibility to install on them the probe monitoring tool.

For network KPI#01 and KPI#02, Ericsson used the CTR (Cell Trace Recording) functionality available in the gNB, which allows after enabling on the node specific PM events, the recollection of cell KPIs per each user that is registered in the 5G cell. The average results of those KPIs were:

- **KPI#01 (UC1 and UC6):** 1,836 Mbps for CPE1 and 251 Mbps for CPE2
- **KPI#02 (UC1 and UC6):** 219 Mbps for CPE1 and 7 Mbps for CPE2
- **KPI#01 (UC10):** 0.861 Mbps for CPE1, 0.868 Mbps for CPE2, 1.259 Mbps for CPE3 and 200 Mbps for CPE4
- **KPI#02 (UC10):** 28 Mbps for CPE1, 28 Mbps for CPE2, 77 Mbps for CPE3 and 60 Mbps for CPE4

A snapshot of the processed results can be seen in the following Figure 37 and Figure 38.

Figure 37. KPI#01 and KPI#02 for each CPE during trial day (UC1 and UC6).

Figure 38. KPI#01 and KPI#02 for each CPE during trial day (UC10).

KPI#03 and KPI#04 were stored and processed from the raw data coming from the gNB counters, that are reported every 15 minutes (also called “ROP” or “Recording output period”). For raw data storage, KPI processing and visualization Ericsson had implemented a Grafana dashboard for both DL and UL aggregated throughput measured in the gNBs, as the example show in Figure 39.

Figure 39. Grafana dashboard example of UC1 for KPI #04 (UL aggregated throughput in the gNB).

The average results for those KPIs are reported in the following:

- **KPI#03 (UC1 and UC6):** 148 Mbps
- **KPI#04 (UC1 and UC6):** 153 Mbps
- **KPI#03 (UC10):** 113 Mbps
- **KPI#04 (UC10):** 171 Mbps

The RTT or round-trip time latency (KPI #08) was measured by using an automated script (Figure 40) in bash, that was launched through the entire duration of the trials, in each CPE. This script was taking every second a RTT measurement from ICMP protocol (ping) considering all possible combinations from CPE_x to CPE_y (CPE1 to CPE2, CPE1 to CPE3 and so on) and from CPE_x to the flight rack application server.

```
#!/bin/bash
# Configuration
USER="root"
PASSWORD="*****"
PREFIX="UC10-YAVE"

monitor_send_their_IPs
declare -A routers
routers["CPE1"]="10.3.203.98"
routers["CPE2"]="10.3.203.106"
routers["CPE3"]="10.3.203.102"
routers["CPE4"]="10.3.203.108"
routers["app-server"]="10.3.203.37"

# List of router pairs that will ping each other
declare -a ping_pairs
ping_pairs=(
  "CPE1 CPE2"
  "CPE2 CPE4"
  "CPE1 CPE4"
  "CPE4 CPE1"
  "CPE4 CPE2"
  "CPE1 CPE3"
  "CPE1 app-server"
  "CPE2 app-server"
  "CPE3 app-server"
  "CPE4 app-server"
)

# Folder for logs on the server
LOG_DIR="show/logs/ping"
mkdir -p "$LOG_DIR"

# Function to start a ping inside tmux
start_ping_session() {
  local src=$1
  local dst=$2
  local status=$3
  local src_ip=${routers[$src]}
  local dst_ip=${routers[$dst]}

  # Validation
  if [[ -z "$src_ip" || -z "$dst_ip" ]]; then
    echo "Error: could not find ip for $src or $dst."
    return
  fi

  local log_name=$(printf "%s%s" "${PREFIX}" "ping_${src}_to_${dst}")
  local log_file="$LOG_DIR/$log_name.log"
  local remote_log_file="/tmp/${log_name}.log"
  local session_name=$(printf "%s%s" "${PREFIX}" "ping_${src}_to_${dst}")

  # Debug: Show the SSH command that will run inside 'tmux'
  echo "DEBUG: $status tmux session for $src -> $dst ($src_ip -> $dst_ip) ====="
  echo "SSH command to be executed: sshpass -p '$PASSWORD' ssh -o StrictHostKeyChecking=no -o ConnectTimeout=5 $USER@$src_ip 'ping $dst_ip | tee -a $remote_log_file'"

  # If the session does not exist, start it with 'bash -c' to properly resolve variables
  if ! tmux has-session -t "$session_name" 2>/dev/null; then
    echo "date: $(date +%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S) - $status session: $session_name | tee -a '$log_file'"

    tmux new-session -d -s "$session_name" \
      "bash -c 'sshpass -p '$PASSWORD' ssh -o StrictHostKeyChecking=no -o ConnectTimeout=5 $USER@$src_ip 'ping $dst_ip | tee -a $remote_log_file' | tee -a $log_file'"
  fi
}
```

Figure 40. Snapshot of bash script for automated KPI #08 recollection.

An example of the measured KPI #08 for UC10 can be seen in the following Figure 41.

Figure 41. Example of UC10 for KPI #08 (RTT latency).

Finally, KPI #17 was also extracted from the gNB counters, measured per NR cell, with the following formula:

$$Av_NrCellAvail = 100 * ((NR_ROP * 900) - (pmCellDowntimeAuto + pmCellDowntimeMan)) / (NR_ROP * 900)$$

being *pmCellDowntimeAuto* the time (in seconds) the cell is automatically disabled (i.e. due to a HW fault or N2 interface link break) and *pmCellDowntimeMan* the time (in seconds) the cell is manually disabled.

This KPI is represented in Figure 42 where 100% of NR cell availability was reported during UC1 and UC6 trials, as an example.

Figure 42. Example of UC1 for KPI #17 (Service availability).

2.4 Romanian cluster

The Romanian cluster hosts the deployment and validation of UC1-Iasi “Smart Crowd Monitoring” and UC4 “Smart Traffic Management” and is mainly based in Iasi, with extensions in Bucharest for the Open Call developments sub-projects, leveraging both the indoor 5G SA infrastructure from the Bucharest and Iasi Orange 5G Labs as well as the outdoor hybrid 5G NSA/SA commercial/private network provided by Orange Romania in the scope of the project.

2.4.1 Final deployment

The final deployment of the 5G and Edge-Compute architecture for UC1 and UC4 was finalized and is indicated in Figure 43, which was updated to reflect the latest version of the technical setup. The 5G architectural considerations were already described in detail in D2.2 [1] and D2.3 [2]. The implementation of this architecture was finalized in the last quarter of 2024, including the coverage extensions in the outdoor area near the Bucharest 5G Lab. In this approach, the RAN equipment that covers the “Stefan cel Mare” pedestrian alley and the “Podu Ros” intersection were configured to support both 5G SA and 5G NSA in an hybrid mode, optimizing dynamically the 5G NR bandwidth allocation depending on the number of 5G UEs connected to the network, with a slight prioritization for the 5G SA ones (20/100 MHz in the n78 band strictly allocated to the 5G SA network). This enables the interconnection with ORO's Bucharest 5G Lab 5G SA Nokia Compact Mobility Unit (CMU) Core Network, facilitating control-plane traffic and access to available Edge Compute resources. Moreover, the Iasi 5G Lab datacenter is the central point of this updated architecture. It hosts a remote 5G SA UPF unit and several Edge Computing servers that host the video analytics applications for UC1 (Iasi) and UC4. The user-plane traffic coming from the Iasi 5G SA RAN units is routed towards the local UPF. In this approach, the video surveillance feeds are transmitted directly to the Iasi 5G Lab datacenter Edge servers over a dedicated Ultra-reliable Low Latency Communication (URLLC) slice that allows for a prioritized latency of about 8 ms E2E.

Furthermore, the final design of the Romanian testbed architecture also included the integration of the VITAL-5G [4] production-ready Network Applications orchestration platform within the Bucharest and Iasi 5G Labs Edge-Cloud facilities. This deployment allows the TUIASI partners and 3rd parties, like the ones that came through the TrialsNet Open Call, to deploy their applications in a more efficient manner, streamlining the process of obtaining access to the needed virtual appliances (Kubernetes pods / VMs). This integration not only showcases the exploitation sustainability of technical solutions developed within research and innovation projects, but also highlights the importance of using user-friendly platforms allowing users outside of the telco space to interact with the network and Edge Computing resources in a programmatic approach.

Moreover, the Iasi video surveillance system is also still using the classic 5G NSA setup for a selected number of terminals in order to have a reference for the comparison with the 5G SA deployment. In this approach, several CPEs deployed in Iasi are still fitted with Orange commercial SIM cards provisioned with the TrialsNet project private APN that is directly connected with the Bucharest and Iasi Edge Computing infrastructure.

Figure 43. Romanian testbed 5G and Edge Compute final architecture.

Finally, as stated previously and showcased in Figure 44, the Bucharest 5G Lab infrastructure was extended to support 5G SA coverage in the outdoor area of the University Politehnica of Bucharest campus, with two new radio sites, with two sectors/site, based on the Ericsson Small Cell solution (Radio 4408), supporting the n78 band; it’s important to note that only 20 MHz of n78 spectrum are allocated for these cells due to the fact that ORO’s commercial 5G infrastructure from the campus area is still based on another vendors’ solution not allowing for the TDD synchronization with the deployed small-cells. This development was performed in order to support the Open Call sub-projects integrating with the Bucharest 5G Lab ecosystem.

Figure 44. Bucharest 5G Lab outdoor coverage extension with 2 sites.

The simulated coverage of the Politehnica of Bucharest campus small-cell sites is showcased in Figure 45 and is encompassing 0.25sqkms. The colors used for drawing the picture have the following significance: green: - 82dBm RSRP (indoor daylight); blue: -93dBm RSRP (in car); red: -98dBm RSRP (outdoor). In terms of performance figures, Figure 45 showcases a best-case scenario (green area - 151 Mbps DL and 26 Mbps UL), while Figure 46 shows a worst-case spot (red area - 58 Mbps DL and 15 Mbps UL).

Figure 45. Bucharest 5G Lab simulated outdoor coverage map.

Figure 46. Bucharest 5G Lab outdoor extension performance (best-case – left / worst-case – right).

The performance of the 5G SA deployment from Iasi was previously assessed in D2.3 [2]. The throughput results that were observed during our testing were hovering around 500 Mbps for DL traffic and 60 Mbps for UL traffic. In terms of actual coverage, Iasi is fully covered by ORO’s 5G network, while the UC1 and UC4 areas are only representing a small percentage of the city, about 0.1sqkms each.

2.4.2 Performed trials

The final trials for the UC1-Iasi and UC4 were performed on the 14th of May 2025 in Iasi. During the day a private showcase event was prepared, featuring participants from the public sector (TUIASI university, Iasi Airport, Special Telecommunication Services) and industry (Continental Automotive, Quartz Matrix). During the event, ORO and TUIASI showcased the visitors the final version of the video analytics applications

developed for implementing UC1 and UC4, as well as the technical specifics of the setup, including network and edge cloud deployment details. At the end of the event KVI questionnaires were given to the attendees and results will be reported in the final WP3 deliverable. A special application-level KPIs collection session was performed at the end of the day.

In terms of the Open Call trials, three sub-projects have been selected for the Romanian cluster (i.e., two Option 1a and one Option 1b) for which ORO provided the following support:

- **Sub-project “AI-PREMSET-MCX” (14-15 April 25):** access to historical RAN performance monitoring datasets and real time monitoring APIs was provided; IPSEC VPN connectivity was established between ORO and Nemergent; target virtualized appliance configuration was discussed and was implemented; laboratory and field tests for the MCX application were performed over 5G NSA (private TrialsNet APN) and 5G SA
- **Sub-project “Augmented Reality” (10-21 March 25):** access to the ORO commercial 5G network was provided with 2 SIM cards provisioned with the private TrialsNet APN, allowing for direct access to the Bucharest 5G Lab Edge Computing facility; 2 additional SIM cards and 5G SA-capable devices were provided; access to one VM with GPU capabilities was provided; access to the 5G Lab Edge Computing facility was provided throughout a VPN client and account; laboratory and field tests for the AR application were performed over 5G NSA and 5G SA
- **Sub-project “AdaptoFlow” (27-31 Jan 2025):** discussions about the capabilities of the Romanian testbed were undergone in order for the AdaptoFlow team to adapt their target PoC; access to the live video camera feeds was provided for testing the video analytics application. The Trial was successfully executed

2.5 Romanian cluster (experimental facilities in Belgium)

As reported in D2.3 [2], the experimental facilities in Belgium comprise several testbeds as small-scale experimental sites located in Antwerp and Ghent, which are used as a complementary setup to the trial site in the Romanian cluster. This setup is used for performing pre-trial research and development activities, which are then transferred to the Romanian trial site for the implementation of the UC4 “Smart Traffic Management”. In addition to that, the experimental facilities in Belgium have been also used to support the Open Call sub-project “6GVision” of Allbesmart and to develop further the Zero-touch Service Management (ZSM) framework through the collaboration between the partners IMEC and NXW. Details on these two activities are reported in the following sub-section.

2.5.1 Final deployment

2.5.1.1 Support to the Open Call sub-project “6GVision”

The overarching goal of the Open Call “6GVision” sub-project was to develop and showcase a proactive beam-switching mechanism for 5G FR2 (mmWave), supported by vision sensing and machine learning. By predicting LOS blockages and dynamically redirecting beams to a reflector, the system effectively overcomes signal loss and ensures robust mmWave communication.

As described in deliverable D2.3 [2], during the first phase of “6GVision” activities, Allbesmart successfully expanded the existing OAI 5G FR1 test network at IMEC to also support FR2 capabilities. Initial trials were conducted using a monolithic gNB setup alongside an OAI user equipment (UE) and later extended to work with a commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) 5G FR2 modem from Quectel. Alongside this, a user-friendly web application was developed to provide intuitive end-to-end control and monitoring of the network.

In the second phase of the activities, the 5G FR2 testbed and web interface were further upgraded to integrate Open RAN (O-RAN) components. The upgrades to the Open5G testbed, enabled through the 6GVision sub-project by Allbesmart at the IMEC premises as shown in Figure 47, are based on the fully open-source and extendable 5G NR OAI stack. The architecture follows a standalone 5G and O-RAN model and is split across two computing platforms: one running the OAI 5G Core Network (CN), the OAI Central Unit (O-CU), and a Near-Real-Time RIC; the other running the OAI Distributed Unit (O-DU). The mid-haul link between the CU and DU uses the 3GPP F1 interface, while the fronthaul between the DU and Radio Unit (RU) implements the O-RAN Split 8 interface.

Figure 47. 5G FR2 infrastructure deployed at the IMEC premises at The Beacon for the 6GVision trial.

For the FR2 front-end, the system uses a USRP for baseband signal processing, paired with an up/down converter and a TMYTEK phased-array beamformer operating in the 28 GHz mmWave band. Signal reflection is handled using the XRifle from TMYTEK—a static beam reflector designed to enhance mmWave coverage, with eight fixed-angle models optimized for different incident and reflection scenarios. The UE used is the Quectel RM530F, an FR2-capable 5G module.

To support vision-assisted operation, the testbed integrates the Nerian Ruby 3D Depth Camera – an advanced stereo vision system tailored for real-time machine vision. This camera captures stereoscopic images and generates accurate depth data with sub-millisecond latency. It works alongside a YOLO-v11-based object detection model, helping predict line-of-sight (LOS) blockage events. OpenCV is used to analyze visual data and detect obstacles between the gNB and the UE, with the depth camera enhancing detection stability.

To respond to predicted blockages, the system employs FlexRIC, a flexible RAN Intelligent Controller, and an xApp developed by the OAI community. This xApp can proactively trigger beam switching toward the static reflector, maintaining reliable signal delivery to the UE.

Overall, the modular architecture deployed directly contributes to the programmability and scalability goals of the 5GOpen testbed. The dashboard-driven network monitoring and control application developed during the trials serves as a user-centric interface for real-time KPI/KVI evaluation, supporting diverse experimentation scenarios across the 5G FR2 spectrum.

2.5.1.2 Final implementation of the ZSM framework

Concerning the final implementation of the ZSM framework, it was successfully integrated into the internal experimentation environment of IMEC, the Smart Highway (SHW) testbed and the LCM infrastructure of NXW. Within the SHW testbed, the ZSM orchestrator supports two distinct operational modes: one optimized for ultra-low latency applications such as smart traffic management, and another tailored for energy efficiency in light-traffic scenarios. These modes allow the framework to dynamically manage multiple metrics with context-aware prioritization. The orchestrator itself runs centrally on a virtual machine hosted at the CMI campus of the University of Antwerp, while also interfacing with the NXW LCM platform in Pisa. This multi-site integration showcases the flexibility and scalability of the ZSM architecture, demonstrating its ability to unify distributed NFVIs under a single, automated service management system as part of the TrialsNet project.

2.5.2 Performed trials

Following initial lab development, the “6GVision” sub-project conducted two integration phases at IMEC facilities in Antwerp. During the first visit in October 2024, they successfully deployed and validated a full end-to-end 5G FR2 setup, integrating a gNB and an early version of the web-based dashboard into the 5GOpen testbed. The priority at this stage was ensuring stable connectivity, with throughput optimization deferred to later stages. Remote access to the infrastructure was granted post-deployment, allowing continued system refinement.

A second visit in March 2025 focused on testing a disaggregated gNB architecture, with the O-CU and O-DU operating on separate compute platforms. Trials addressed three key aspects: FR2 indoor coverage performance,

NLOS coverage enhancement via mmWave reflectors, and LOS blockage mitigation using a vision-aided gNB. Across these scenarios, comprehensive KPIs - including bitrate, RTT, RSRP, SINR, and BLER - were collected alongside user-centric KVI's related to dashboard usability. Details will be reported in the final D5.3 deliverable.

In controlled indoor settings, the 28 GHz gNB demonstrated consistent signal quality over a 40 m corridor, covering an estimated area of 838 m². Reflector-based tests revealed significant performance gains under NLOS conditions, with signal metrics improved by up to 20 dB and throughput restored to 200 Mbps downlink and 100 Mbps uplink. In LOS blockage scenarios, the vision-enhanced gNB effectively forecasted disruptions, confirming the need for proactive beam-switching mechanisms in mmWave deployments.

While not large-scale in user terms, the trial's breadth of configurations and depth of measurement make it a substantial contribution at this TRL stage. Enhancements to the OAI 5G FR2 stack, developed through this work, are now publicly available and enable reproducibility with off-the-shelf hardware. These contributions not only strengthen the open-source ecosystem but also lay the groundwork for advanced 6G experimentation within the 5GOpen testbed.

2.6 Greek cluster

This section provides the final view of the Greek cluster private infrastructure where the pre-trial tests of UC2 "Proactive Public Infrastructure Assets Management", UC3 "Autonomous APRON", UC6 "Mass Casualty Incident (MCI) and Emergency Rescue in Populated Area", UC11 "Service Robots for Enhanced Passenger's Experience", and UC13 "Extended Reality (XR) Museum Experience" have been performed.

2.6.1 Final deployment

The deployment of the WINGS private network was finalized since the previous deliverable D2.3 [2]. During the recent period, specific pre-trial tests have been conducted for evaluating the performance before the trial execution on field. Downlink/uplink throughput, round-trip and one-way latency have been assessed for UC2, UC3, UC6 and UC11 in the WINGS private network.

The WINGS private testbed architecture and components were described in D2.3 [2]. Networking components included the installation of 3 dedicated small cells (see Figure 48) and the respective baseband units based on 3GPP Rel-15 (with potential for upgrading to Rel-16) and routers in the WINGS premises. The cells are accessible for testing with private SIM cards and are not accessible with public SIM cards. The coverage area of the pre-trial tests which took place in the WINGS private infrastructure is 600 square meters.

Figure 48. Final WINGS private testbed architecture and photos from installation of small cells.

2.6.2 Performed trials

As previously mentioned, the WINGS private infrastructure was used in the project for the pre-trial tests of various use cases which final trial have been then performed at the Athens International Airport (AIA), the City of Athens (Technopolis area), and Corinth Canal over the 5G public network. In particular:

- **UC2 (AIA and Technopolis):** In this use case the connectivity of the autonomous robot/AGV and the transmission of streaming videos to the WINGS platform was tested before the actual trial.
- **UC3 (AIA):** In this use case the connectivity of the autonomous robot/AGV and the transmission of streaming videos to the WINGS platform was tested before the actual trial.
- **UC6 (Technopolis):** In this use case the connectivity of wearables, health devices and their transmission of data to the WINGS platform was tested before the actual trial.
- **UC11 (AIA):** In this use case the connectivity of the streaming thermal cameras, of the humanoid robot and the transmission of streaming data to the WINGS platform was tested before the actual trial.
- **UC13 (Technopolis and Corinth Canal museum):** In this use case the connectivity of AR/VR devices and their transmission of data to the WINGS platform was tested before the actual trial.

Details on the performed trials and related results will be reported in the final D3.3, D4.3, and D5.3 deliverables.

In addition, the Open Call sub-project “MILESTONE” has been part of the Greek cluster as an Option 1b and was designed to support surveillance equipment control as well as continuous monitoring of the working environment using data streamed through the public 5G network. The project used a public 5G network and does not intervene with the settings of the network. However, the trial itself took place in Athens (Technopolis area) as an extension of the UC2 of TrialsNet.

3 TrialsNet’s infrastructures extension through the Open Call

This section summarizes the final deployment of the infrastructure (including the connectivity aspects) of seven Option 2 sub-projects that have been particularly innovative and impactful from the design, implementation and deployment perspectives. In particular, this section lists how these sub-projects implemented and experimented advanced 5G and B5G platform and network solutions in the context of their activities. In addition to what provided by TrialsNet, these efforts provide a different point of view on how to address and assess the three project’s domains, offering a comprehensive view of the characteristics required by next-generation networks.

3.1 Infrastructure description

The network infrastructure deployed across the sub-projects ranged from commercial public networks to fully customized private 5G cores. The following Table 2 summarizes the sub-projects discussed in this section, the ones that rely on experimental or large-scale infrastructures.

Table 2. Network deployment from different sub-projects.

Sub-project	Core Network	RAN Components	Deployment Type
AI4RTC	Cosmote 5G SA (Commercial)	External 5G router (ZTE MC801A)	Commercial
5GS3	Open5GS (Dockerized)	CableFree gNB (2x2 MIMO)	Private
Football Stadium	Stadicom Proprietary Core	Sparq-2025-SRU + DAM modules	Hybrid Commercial / Private
Connected Rails	Commercial MNO (Italy)	USRP E312 SDR, Shared gNB	Hybrid Commercial / Private
MediVision	Open5GS + HA Mini-PC	Askey SCE2120 (CU/DU)	Experimental
ATOS	TNO B5G Core (Rel-17)	Ericsson gNB, Edge Servers	Experimental
METACLINIC	Turkcell Experimental Core	Ericsson AIR 5322 AAU	Experimental

In “AI4RTC”, the integration of external 5G routers into legacy EV charging stations enabled a significant improvement in operational latency, achieving sub-second responsiveness in charging load commands. This was made possible through the Cosmote 5G standalone network, bypassing the limitations of embedded 3G/4G modules.

The “5GS3” sub-project designed and deployed a full private 5G SA network using Open5GS on a containerized virtual infrastructure. Although regulatory constraints prevented deployment at Athens International Airport, the fallback to a commercial 5G network enabled comprehensive testing of robotic and video surveillance applications in real-world conditions, proving the viability of open-source core network solutions.

In the “Football Stadium” sub-project, a hybrid setup combined a public NSA 5G network with a dedicated SA private slice operated by Stadicom. The system supported high-density user scenarios, enabling real-time delivery of personalized services, live video feeds, and interactive fan engagement features. Notably, seamless integration between the public and private networks allowed end-users to transparently transition between connectivity layers.

The “Connected Rails” sub-project installed two parallel systems (SYS-NGAP and SYS-SDR) within a moving tram. While SYS-NGAP facilitated real-time sensor data transmission over a commercial 5G network, SYS-SDR collected passive RF signal samples using a USRP E312 device. The co-location and synchronization of these systems enabled detailed offline signal analysis, directly correlated to tram geolocation.

“MediVision” deployed a compact, self-contained 5G-SA-in-a-box system composed of an integrated CU/DU remote radio unit and a miniaturized Open5GS core. The architecture was tailored for medical environments, offering traffic slicing and edge computing capabilities, and incorporated fallback Wi-Fi 6 access via OpenWiFi

APs for areas lacking licensed spectrum. This highly portable system proved suitable for in-hospital deployments and future scalability.

For the “ATOS” sub-project, trials were conducted using the FNS 6G national testbed in the Netherlands. The architecture incorporated an edge-deployed B5G core (the architecture is depicted in Figure 49, which highlights the integration with the Belgian facilities discussed in Section 2.5) with exposed APIs for real-time monitoring and orchestration. The successful remote operation of a vehicle over the 5G SA link demonstrated not only ultra-low latency but also the effectiveness of automated Quality-on-Demand mechanisms tied to energy-aware orchestration.

Figure 49. Network architectures of the ATOS sub-project.

Finally, “METACLINIC” established a mmWave directional link between the mainland and a remote island clinic, achieving stable, high-throughput transmission over a 7.5 km sea crossing. Using experimental infrastructure provided by Turkcell, this setup demonstrated the potential of mmWave beamforming to support immersive telehealth applications in geographically isolated regions.

3.2 Connectivity aspects

The “5GS3” sub-project’s deployment (see Figure 50) leveraged the upper n77 band (3.8–4.2 GHz) and a 100 MHz channel centered at 3.9 GHz, simulating differentiated QoS services via logical slicing.

Figure 50. Network connectivity for the “5GS3” sub-project.

In the “AI4RTC” sub-project, replacing wireless and legacy modem connections with Ethernet-linked 5G routers (see Figure 51) led to substantial improvements in reliability and command execution latency. This was critical for maintaining safe EV charging under dynamic load conditions.

Figure 51. Deployment of the “AI4RTC” sub-project.

In “ATOS” sub-project, the testbed employed multiple licensed bands (n77, B3, B28) with both SA and NSA support. Coverage was optimized through massive MIMO configurations over a 210 m × 60 m area, allowing consistent uplink throughput sufficient for vehicle teleoperation. On-demand performance tuning was automated based on throughput thresholds. Figure 50 shows the network connectivity area.

The “Football Stadium” sub-project’s dual connectivity model ensured continuity of service. Spectators initially accessed public 5G NSA services, then transitioned into the stadium’s private SA environment through a custom application. This allowed for precise content delivery, low-latency streaming, and direct food/merchandise ordering (as envisioned by the use case) with minimal service interruptions.

For “Connected Rails”, the dual-system approach was driven by practical limitations: a shared antenna was physically switched between the data transmission (SYS-NGAP) and RF signal collection (SYS-SDR) phases. Passive signal collection spanned all commercial 5G bands in Italy, and time synchronization ensured that data could be correlated to position with high precision.

The sub-project “MediVision” relied on up to 100 MHz channels in bands n48, n77, and n78, with fallback support to OpenWiFi-based 4x4 MU-MIMO access points. The flexibility of adapting to local licensing conditions while maintaining comparable UX through Wi-Fi slice emulation was key to its utility in real-world hospital environments.

Finally, “METACLINIC” operated both sub-6 GHz and mmWave links, with one trial establishing a high-throughput directional beam over a maritime LOS of 7.5 km. The performance and resilience of this link provided evidence of mmWave’s viability in bridging underserved remote zones with immersive health services.

3.3 Main remarks from the sub-projects’ activities

Across the experimental sub-projects, a clear set of themes emerged that reflect the work performed to deploy 5G solutions tailored to specific verticals. One of the most consistent operations was the need to enforce hardware retrofitting. This was particularly evident in the deployment of external 5G routers and Wi-Fi connections. In this case the result was a drastic reduction in latency that can be finally implemented when fully fledged 5G SA CPEs will be available on the market.

Another critical point was the operational maturity of private 5G networks, especially when implemented with open-source software. The sub-projects efforts show that private 5G solutions can be realistically deployed, maintained, and scaled by non-operator entities when designed with open standards and cloud-native principles.

Latency-sensitive applications like vehicle teleoperation highlighted not only the capabilities of 5G in controlled testbeds but also the importance of end-to-end orchestration. In such trials, performance thresholds were monitored in real time and used to trigger adaptive quality policies, ensuring stable connectivity and command responsiveness even under fluctuating channel conditions.

Use cases that combined public and private networks, were also important. This type of solution was especially important for deployments in large venues. Seamless transitions between network slices and connectivity domains enabled rich, low-latency services to be delivered to hundreds of users without user-side reconfiguration. This showed that hybrid architectures mixing private 5G infrastructure with public ones is highly effective for scenarios with bursty demand and localized services.

4 Final implementation of TrialsNet's innovations and results

As discussed already in D2.2 [1] and D2.3 [2], TrialsNet identified a set of innovation that either targets the network deployment activities horizontally (i.e., designed for a specific cluster, for all the use cases) or vertically (i.e., for one or a set of use cases). In the following, the final implementation for each innovation is described, detailing the associated KPIs and the already carried out validation activities.

4.1 Horizontal Innovations

The solutions discussed in this section target the Belgian cluster and the activities associated with the Spanish one. In particular, the ZSM framework and the B5G application development have been important aspects for the development of the ITSS domain use cases and related sub-projects as well as part of project's contribution to the 3GPP standardization (see Section 0).

4.1.1 Zero-touch Service Management

The objective is to showcase the ZSM framework's ability to handle multiple use cases concurrently while dynamically allocating resources in edge computing environments. This ensures optimal performance and seamless service delivery for critical applications. The focus is on refining resource allocation while maintaining key QoS KPIs, such as E2E latency and power consumption, aligning with energy-aware resource management to enhance the network's sustainability. Through cross-domain orchestration, the flexibility and scalability of the ZSM framework are highlighted in autonomously managing diverse network environments and addressing challenges like vendor lock-in and interoperability.

Figure 52. NXW LCM platform and the SHW testbed ZSM Integration.

The primary features demonstrated in this integration include:

- Cross-domain orchestration for simultaneous management of multiple use cases and dynamic resource allocation in edge computing, facilitated by intent-based communication and real-time standardization of data structures
- Autonomous decision-making and zero-touch service management to optimize resource utilization and ensure seamless service continuity for critical applications
- Self-configuration of managed services and network resources to autonomously adapt to evolving conditions and requirements, including dynamic onboarding or offboarding of NFVI environments
- Edge computing resource allocation for intelligent traffic management.

To validate the framework’s capabilities in managing multiple domains under dynamic conditions, two technological infrastructures are employed, as depicted in Figure 52: the SHW testbed in Antwerp, Belgium, dedicated to wireless networking research, and the Nextworks LCM infrastructure in Pisa, Italy, utilized for edge computing resource allocation in UC4 “Smart Traffic Management” camera services.

4.1.1.1 Final development

The ZSM Framework is designed with a modular architecture, allowing its components to be deployed independently or collectively to accommodate various use cases. It incorporates the following essential inner unit components, as illustrated in Figure 53:

- **ZSM Publisher:** Extracts and transmits performance data from computing, network, and energy nodes for monitoring purposes. Additionally, it provides NFVI specifications—such as identity, location, and deployment—available for subscription.
- **ZSM Subscriber:** Receives performance metrics and NFVI specifications (identity, location, deployment) from NFVI environments, structuring the datasets for near real-time monitoring and decision-making.
- **ZSM Orchestrator:** Aggregates data from multiple ZSM Publishers and ZSM Subscribers across various NFVI environments, formulates decisions, and communicates deployment instructions to ZSM Deployers.
- **ZSM Deployer:** Implements the directives provided by the ZSM Orchestrator after decisions are finalized. This includes executing various operational actions such as scaling up or down, terminating services, and instantiating new instances to optimize resource utilization and network performance.

Figure 53. High-level architecture of the ZSM Framework its technological enablers.

The framework's modules can be initialized without specifying IP addresses, preventing disruptions caused by dynamic IP assignments. This enables automatic scaling of both nodes and NFVI subscribed to the orchestrator, enhancing flexibility in ZSM framework deployment and in the subscription or checkout of entities like publishers. To leverage this communication approach, message datasets are structured using normalized and generic data formats, ensuring various NFVI provide metrics in a standardized manner and simplifying integration across diverse environments as presented in Figure 54.

Figure 54. Example of a standardized message for cross-domain data exchange in the ZSM Framework.

The ZSM Framework orchestrates multiple domain environments and, within the SHW testbed, is structured into two priority-based sections. The first section optimizes E2E latency for mission-critical applications involving vehicular traffic such as UC4 “Smart Traffic Management”, while the second prioritizes lower power consumption, making it suitable for light traffic scenarios. Both sections facilitate decision-making processes that manage multiple metric sets simultaneously based on their importance. Additionally, a third section integrates the NXW LCM platform located in Pisa, Italy. The ZSM orchestrator operates within the ZSM Central virtual machine at the CMI campus of the University of Antwerp as seen in Figure 52, where it collects and processes metrics from both the SHW testbed and the NXW LCM platform.

4.1.1.2 KPIs validation

The ZSM framework has been assessed within the context of UC4 “Smart Traffic Management” to enhance resource allocation while maintaining the performance of key QoS KPIs. Specifically, two critical indicators are highlighted:

- **E2E latency:** this KPI is vital for meeting the stringent requirements of mission-critical applications
- **Power consumption:** this KPI plays a crucial role in achieving energy-efficient operation across the managed infrastructure

By focusing on these KPIs, the ZSM framework demonstrates its capability to dynamically balance performance and efficiency in real-world edge computing environments.

In this context, E2E latency refers to the total time required for a data packet or service request to travel from the source (e.g., a vehicular user or sensor) to the destination (e.g., an edge computing node or service endpoint)

and back. This metric is essential for mission-critical and real-time applications, as it directly affects the responsiveness and reliability of the services provided.

Additionally, power consumption denotes the total electrical energy used by the edge computing nodes and network infrastructure involved in service delivery. Monitoring and optimizing power consumption is fundamental for enabling energy-aware resource allocation and improving network sustainability.

To measure E2E latency the 100 ms threshold was chosen as seen in Table 3, because it aligns with the stringent requirements of mission-critical services in vehicular networks, which is essential for applications like collision avoidance and real-time traffic updates. Given the critical nature of the vehicular application involving interaction with VRUs, E2E latency is established as the primary metric to ensure ultra-low latency and high reliability. However, when the E2E latency between the user (vehicle) and multiple Edge Computing nodes reaches similar values, power consumption becomes the decisive factor, prioritizing the node with lower energy usage. This approach validates the feasibility of incorporating power consumption metrics into decision-making, opening the door to more advanced strategies for the sustainable management of Edge Computing infrastructure in the long term.

For the measurements of the energy consumption like presented in Table 3, 60 watts represents the average energy consumption limit for a RSU under standard operational conditions. This threshold is essential for ensuring energy efficiency while maintaining reliable performance in vehicular service orchestration. Table 4 reports the validation of this E2E latency.

Table 3. KPI evaluation target per NFVI.

Scenario	NFVI	KPI	Threshold
Vehicular Services	SHW – A	E2E Latency	100 ms
Energy-aware Resource Allocation	SHW – B	Energy	60 wt
Smart Traffic Camera Services	NXW LCM	E2E Latency	100 ms

Table 4. ZSM KPIs Validation.

Measurement ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
ZSM-KPI-01	End-to-end network latency after ZSM intervention	Latency reduced from 40 ms to ~15 ms post-QoD activation	Target achieved. Confirmed benefit of ZSM in maintaining latency-sensitive service quality.

The experimentation conducted across the SHW and NXW infrastructures, as a complementary experimentation environment for testing enablers for UC4, are detailed in the following points:

- **Previous Conditions:** All service instances hosted on Edge Computing nodes operated under fixed resource configurations, potentially leading to underperformance or resource overprovisioning.
- **Objective:** To dynamically allocate computing and network resources based on priorities, ensuring that QoS requirements for services deployed on Edge Computing nodes are met.
- **Expected Behavior:** Simultaneous cross-domain multi-criteria decision-making, with automatic adjustment of vehicular service resources according to network conditions.
- **Observed Behavior:** The ZSM orchestrator successfully adapts KPI priorities based on the NFVI in different sections of SHW. In Section-A of SHW, E2E latency is prioritized first, followed by power consumption to support mission-critical vehicular services with an energy-aware approach. In Section-B, where vehicular and network traffic demand is lower, power consumption takes precedence over E2E latency. In the NXW infrastructure, E2E latency remains the primary focus alongside computing resources such as CPU.
- **Aftermath Conditions:** The ZSM orchestrator effectively selects the optimal node for service deployment based on KPI values, enabling dynamic resource adjustments for vehicular services.

Table 5 provides a snapshot of the decision-making process, illustrating how the orchestrator selects the optimal node for service deployment based on KPI values. The CPU measurement units obtained from the data vary between the SHW testbed and the NXW LCM infrastructure due to differences in their respective LCM configurations. However, these variations do not impact decision-making outcomes, as the process remains agnostic by design. This approach allows each NFVI to independently establish its priorities and metrics while ensuring seamless and simultaneous management within the framework.

Table 5. Snapshot of decision-making for multiple domain orchestration.

NFVI	MEC Unit	CPU	Power	E2E Latency
SHW – A	RSU2	4%	55 wt	51.177 ms
SHW – B	RSU5	5%	56 wt	51.211 ms
NXW LCM	K8s-cluster-4	1.7 u	-	85.903 ms

Table 6 highlights that RSU nodes exhibit significantly higher decision counts (e.g., RSU6: 3450, RSU1: 2762) compared to Kubernetes clusters, which reach a maximum of 897 decisions for k8s-cluster-4. The RSUs in the SHW testbed likely process real-time vehicular data, triggering frequent orchestration decisions, whereas the NXW infrastructure appears to prioritize stability, resulting in fewer adjustments. This contrast reveals how autonomous orchestration impacts different NFVIs, with the high decision rates in SHW reflecting closed-loop control adapting to edge dynamics.

Table 6. Cross-domain decision-making metrics for NFVI nodes under stress conditions.

Node ID	Decision Count	Avg CPU (%)	Avg Power (W)	E2E Latency (ms)
cluster-1 (NXW)	238	0	-	95.6
cluster-2 (NXW)	797	1.8	-	97.1
cluster-3 (NXW)	821	1	-	90.9
cluster-4 (NXW)	897	0	-	83.4
RSU1 (SHW-A)	2762	4	49.2	102.3
RSU2 (SHW-A)	802	4	55.5	96.3
RSU3 (SHW-A)	2200	4	54.6	102.9
RSU4 (SHW-B)	700	4.9	52.9	103
RSU6 (SHW-B)	3450	4.3	51.3	102.1
RSU7 (SHW-B)	1129	4.6	52.1	102.4

Finally, Table 7 summarizes key experimental results, aligning with the capabilities of the ZSM framework. The decision metrics indicate distinct operational patterns between SHW and NXW nodes, showcasing the framework's autonomous orchestration capacity in dynamic edge environments. Additionally, multiple CPU unit measurements reinforce the ZSM framework's multi-criteria decision-making capability. Power metrics (49-59W for RSUs, unavailable for Kubernetes clusters) highlight an energy-awareness gap in core infrastructure monitoring while still demonstrating efforts toward sustainable network management. Collectively, these findings emphasize the ZSM framework's cross-domain adaptability, integrating diverse metrics and decision-making processes, and showcasing its potential for future 6G networks.

Table 7. Summary of Key Results.

Metrics	RSUs (SHW)	K8s Clusters (NXW)	ETSI ZSM
Decisions	High (2762-3450)	Low (238-897)	Autonomous orchestration
CPU	Stable (4%)	Idle (0-1.8 u)	Agnostic metrics management

E2E Latency	Higher (96-103 ms)	Lower (83-97 ms)	QoS tradeoffs per domain
Power	Partial (49-59 Wt)	Missing	Energy-awareness gap

4.1.2 B5G application framework

Concerning the B5G Application Framework that was reported in D2.3 [2], this horizontal innovation is further progressed upon in the context of the ZSM framework and its integration with the infrastructures described in the previous sections, as well as the energy-aware design. The progress is currently focused on progressing of embedding the energy-awareness in the application logic and standardizing this approach in the form of an overarching application package, which was previously described in D2.2 [1], and D2.3 [2]. The results of these activities will be reported in the last WP3 in the context of UC4 showcasing the impact of energy-awareness.

4.1.3 Digital Twins applied to next generation mobile networks

The previous deliverable D2.2 [1] described the use of Digital Twins (DTs) for the design of next-generation mobile networks. Thanks to DTs it is possible to create synchronized virtual replicas of real-world systems (which can be network functions, network services, or specific pieces of hardware), enabling better AI/ML-driven automation, network management, and performance optimization.

4.1.3.1 Final development

In particular, D2.2 [1] presented a scenario where different use cases for the application of DTs were presented:

- **DTs for Network Appliances:** Simulating network components like virtualized RAN (vRAN) to optimize operations
- **DTs for Network Services:** Creating digital replicas of network services for enhanced orchestration
- **DTs for the Network Environment:** Capturing environmental factors that impact network performance

In the context of TrialsNet, and the specific validation environment in the 5Tonic lab, followed in D2.2 [1] with the description of a possible solution for the latter scenario.

Deliverable D2.2 [1] detailed the design, development, and testing of a DT for a virtualized RAN system, using open-source tools, in the context of the development activities carried out in the Spanish cluster. In our design, the DT models the computing resources availability, elapsed decoding time, according to contextual data used for scheduling decisions such as the size of the uplink frames and the signal-to-noise conditions in vRAN environments.

In D2.2 [1] a Neural Network (NN)-based model has been proposed as DT for predictions, using data coming from a gNB implemented as Open Source. Among the challenges that were tackled:

- **Real-Time Synchronization:** Ensuring DTs remain up-to-date with physical networks requires efficient data collection and processing techniques
- **Data Complexity & Adaptability:** DTs must handle unforeseen changes (e.g., sudden CPU shortages). The paper demonstrates an adaptive DT model capable of learning and adjusting to new conditions
- **AI/ML Integration:** DTs can improve model training, monitoring, and decision-making in AI-driven network operations, reducing costly real-world testing

DTs are hence a very important enabler for 6G networks, facilitating real-time monitoring, automation, and optimization. The results highlight how a well-designed DT can accurately reflect the behavior of a physical system and adapt to dynamic network conditions.

This innovation focuses on modeling the behavior of a Forward Error Correction (FEC) decoder within a virtualized Radio Access Network (vRAN) environment. The goal is to develop a DT that accurately replicates the real system's behavior in terms of decoding time and success, enabling effective interaction with AI/ML-based MAC schedulers. To construct the DT, the input parameters that influence the decoder's performance were identified: CPU capacity, signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), modulation and coding scheme (MCS) index, and the number of physical resource blocks (PRBs). The output of interest includes a binary indicator for decoding

success (CRC) and the decoding time. These outputs are modeled in the DT as the probability of successful decoding and a normally distributed decoding time with estimated mean and standard deviation.

For dataset collection, a controlled experimental setup using srsRAN has been developed, an open-source LTE/5G software suite, to emulate a realistic radio access network. They automate the variation of the input parameters (SNR, CPU capacity, MCS, and PRB configuration) across their domains, generating around 14 million samples. The decoding operation is measured by directly monitoring the execution time and CRC result, while system noise is minimized by pinning decoding threads to dedicated CPU cores. This comprehensive dataset forms the foundation for training the DT model. Overall, the DT design not only reflects the performance distribution of the real decoder but also provides a reliable synthetic environment for training and evaluating resource-aware AI/ML algorithms in future mobile networks. The associated KPIs assess the quality of the Digital Twin in terms of

4.1.3.2 KPIs validation

This innovation has been deployed in the 5TONIC Lab, as part of the activities associated with the Spanish cluster. The full validation methodology has been discussed in [14] while Table 8 reports the main results.

Table 8. DT for mobile networks KPIs validation.

Measurement ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
DT-KPI-1	DT should predict decoding success probability accurately, related to KPI#10 (Accuracy)	DT achieves low BCE loss, effectively learning trends of decoding success rates	Passed, small error only in transition regions
DT-KPI-2	DT should adapt to unseen computing availability changes, related to KPI#12 (Recall)	DT successfully re-trained and adjusted when CPU capacity distribution changed	Passed, loss initially spiked but stabilized
DT-KPI-3	DT inference should be significantly faster than real-time measurement. Related to KPI#9 (Latency)	DT inference time = 2.8 μ s per sample, 350 \times speed increase with respect to a real decoding	Passed, faster than physical system measurements

4.2 Vertical Innovations

This Section discusses the vertical innovations associated with some specific Use Cases.

4.2.1 AI mechanisms for diagnostics and resources efficiency

6G will support the delivery of solutions for verticals which will rely on various distributed AI components in the infrastructure. AI is part of the innovations enabled by 6G technology. TrialsNet conducts work on enhanced AI mechanisms to ensure that the proper performance is delivered in compliance with the needed requirements.

4.2.1.1 Final development

Framed in this context, in UC2 “Proactive Public Infrastructure Assets Management” the following developments have taken place:

- **AI Module Integration:** In UC2 a specific intelligence module is activated to process the video feed (frames from a camera) and make any necessary detections and calculations. The algorithm is able to detect various types of damages and calculates their severity. How the module works is explained in the steps below:
 - Step 1: As the sequence of images (video/stream) is given as an input, every frame passes through the Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) Algorithm. This algorithm is used to improve the contrast of the image.

- Step 2: An object detection model based on the YOLOv8 architecture is built. This model can detect multiple objects in a single image. The analysis of a video/stream is therefore performed frame-by-frame.
- Step 3: The preprocessed frame is given as an input to the model and the detections are the output of the model. For each individual input frame, the detected damage's cropped image and the damage's class are collected along with the frame ID and frame shape. For a configurable frame window, this information is collected and passed to the postprocessing stage.
- **Development Operations (DevOps):** Development of each component took place as a dockerised service for ease of deployment of the services using latest technologies such as docker and docker compose inside a Virtual Machine (VM).
- **Analytics and Diagnostics:** Analytics are used for assessing the condition of the pavement and identifying damage through image processing. In the measurement results below, we show the algorithm accuracy for the detection of damages.

4.2.1.2 KPIs validation

In order to validate the KPIs related to the AI mechanism, the network setup described in Table 9 has been used.

Table 9. The mobile network setup used to evaluate the AI mechanism.

Asset	Value
3GPP Release	15
Architecture	NSA
Band (GHz)	3.5
Bandwidth (MHz)	150
Coverage type	Outdoor
Devices used	Streaming cameras x 2, Robot with On-Board Unit (OBU) x 1, Laptops x 2

For the collection of results, the robot reported in Figure 55 was utilized in order to run in selected areas of the AIA in which UC2 took place. The streaming cameras on the robot, obtained images of the ground and transmitted information for further processing and identification of potential cracks, holes etc.

Figure 55. Robot utilised in UC2 trial.

According to the measurements the following KPIs are relevant to AI mechanisms for diagnostics and resources efficiency:

- **KPI#10 (Accuracy):** Proportion of correct predictions made by the algorithm
- **KPI#11 (Precision):** How often the algorithm is correct when it predicts a positive outcome

The measurement results which are provided in the table that follows show that met the needed requirements:

Table 10. Measurement results.

Measurement ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
2.1_Field01_01	KPI#10: 0.85	0.88	Comply
2.1_Field01_01	KPI#11: 0.80	0.85	Comply

4.2.2 Automatic orchestration of network slices to ensure QoS in mobility

In network management, services are classified by their criticality:

- **Mission critical services:** services that demand ultra-high availability (99.999%) and low latency to prevent immediate risk of human life, such as in medical emergencies, and must always remain operational.
- **Business critical services:** services that are vital for financial stability, requiring high with disruptions causing significant monetary losses.
- **Non-critical services:** services that have flexible performance requirements, focusing more on survivability than strict service levels.

In some cases, mission critical services must be deployable “on the fly” within minutes and over ad-hoc deployment areas. The UC8 “Smart Ambulance” provides a clear example. This unpredictable, rapid activation requires a highly robust and flexible network infrastructure capable of adapting instantly to changing demands.

The ER Innovative Orchestrator (simply referred to as “orchestrator” in the following) deployed in TrialsNet has a vital role in ensuring service differentiation by managing and coordinating network resources dynamically based on the priority and criticality of different services. It enables the implementation of QoS policies, allocates bandwidth efficiently, and enforces SLAs tailored to mission critical, business critical, and non-critical services. Service differentiation is considered a prerequisite for network monetization because the ability to offer differentiated services allows CSP to offer premium services to consumers and business customers and to monetize their investment in 5G infrastructure effectively.

5G SA provides the capability to associate a service with a slice. This feature offers the opportunity to differentiate services beyond just bandwidth and transmission speed. Such differentiation can include latency, spatial requirements, and application-specific needs. The orchestrator developed in TrialsNet, leveraging on the 5G SA capability, includes new functions that allow associating a service with a slice in a specific geographical area and manage it as E2E including the transport domain. The performances ensured in the radio domain is also effectively preserved across the transport domain where the orchestrator can guarantee the KPIs without the need of over-provisioning.

To ensure the required QoS while optimizing resource usage, an Admission Control (AC) function is introduced. This function is based on the KPI values agreed upon during the service provisioning phase and allows the transport network to be configured accordingly. The AC check the entering traffic in the transport network per service and cut the traffic in case of KPI violation. Moreover, the orchestrator can re-route the traffic in other path to deal with congestion.

The orchestrator has been tested with concurrent use cases trials in the Pisa Cluster, ensuring service differentiation via dynamic Differentiated Services Code Point (DSCP) and 5G QoS Indicators (5QI) mapping and AC. DSCP is a field in the IP header to classify and manage network traffic by assigning different priority levels to packets. 5QI are standardized numeric identifiers used in 5G networks to define the QoS characteristics of a data flow. Each 5QI value corresponds to a set of parameters such as priority level, packet delay budget, and packet error rate.

Two different services with different bandwidth needs could be mapped on the same DSCP in the transport node (router) but being subject to two different policies to handle the ingress bandwidth or a same service can require different association of 5QI-DSCP. Distinguishing traffic per service type in transport requires to consider an additional tag than DSCP. For example, in case of IPv6 traffic, the indication of the service type could be included in the Flow Label field [19]; in case of Segment Routing SRV6 [20] and MPLS-TE [21] the indication could be inferred by the Segment Identifier and the MPLS label, respectively. Moreover, the service differentiation can be implemented per interface. In this case the ingress interface of the transport network is associated to a service. Such techniques require further extensions which are currently under definition in IETF, e.g. in [22].

The orchestrator has been successfully implemented and its capability of concurrently supporting multiple use cases (UC7, UC8, and U9), including the open call use case COMO5, has been demonstrated in field tests. In the most challenging test, critical patient traffic has been prioritized, maintaining stable performance even under a congestion scenario emulated through “disturbance” traffic as detailed in the following sub-section.

4.2.2.1 Final development

To guarantee E2E QoS, each service is explicitly mapped to a 5QI and to a DSCP in the transport network. Several extensions, beyond those found in current 5G solutions, have been added to the orchestrator. During service provisioning, the 5QI selected for the RAN and CN is automatically linked to the matching DSCP value in the transport layer.

The correspondence between the profiles associated with each use case and the related 5QIs was also defined. As reported in Table 11, each 5QI is mapped to a corresponding DSCP (Differentiated Services Code Point) that will be used in the transport network to differentiate the priorities of the various traffics.

Table 11. Scheme profiles association with 5QI and DSCP.

Use Case	5QI	DSCP	Area
UC7 “Remote Proctoring”	80	AF21 (DSCP 18)	Indoor
COMO5 “Continuous Monitoring of Chronic Patients” (stable mode)	80	AF21 (DSCP 18)	Indoor/Outdoor
UC8 - Smart Ambulance	80	AF21 (DSCP 18)	Outdoor
UC9 “Adaptive Control of Hannes Prosthetic Device”	5	CS5 (DSCP 40)	Indoor
COMO5 “Continuous Monitoring of Chronic Patients” (deteriorating mode)	5	CS5 (DSCP 40)	Indoor/Outdoor

5QI 5 is associated with CS5 (Class Selector). CS5 supports high-priority traffic like VoIP (Voice over IP) or real-time communication, where low latency and jitter are crucial. 5QI 80 is associated with AF21 (Assured Forwarding). AF21 is designed to guarantee delivery under certain conditions Medium-priority traffic like some streaming, business-critical data that’s not delay-sensitive.

When a new service request is made, the orchestrator takes several key steps to ensure that the service meets its performance requirements. At first, it evaluates the necessary network requirements, such as the maximum latency and the throughput needed to support the service. Based on such needs, the orchestrator chooses a 5QI and map it to a DSCP value. Through the transport controller (e.g., SDN) the orchestrator checks if sufficient network resources (bandwidth, processing capacity, etc.) on the transport: routers within the transport domain then only need to inspect the DSCP value in packet headers to apply the appropriate forwarding treatment, ensuring the required QoS without needing to understand 5QI directly. This process allows the network to dynamically allocate resources and prioritize traffic efficiently, maintaining high service quality for different applications.

With this technique, the orchestrator has mapped a service on a specific E2E slice and associate the corresponding 5QI-DSCP pair. Moreover, the orchestrator can modify dynamically the specific 5QI-DSCP pair for the considered service belonging to a specific slice. For example, in COMO5 trial, a service can switch dynamically between profile stable mode (5QI 80-AF21) and deteriorating mode (5QI 5-CS5) and vice versa while remaining associated to the same slice and additional logic allows a service to change its 5QI-DSCP mapping dynamically. The transport-network orchestration component has been fully implemented and validated: tests reported in the following confirm that AC and on-the-fly configuration of transport nodes work as intended.

Figure 56 illustrates the test setup which includes a RAN baseband (RAN BB) system connected to an aggregation router (R6675-RAN), and a core router (R6675-CORE). The aggregation router connects to the core router via two links, LINK1 and LINK2. A test PC (PC1 TREX) is connected to both the routers. TREX is a popular open-source, high-performance traffic generator developed by Cisco.

Figure 56. ER Innovative Orchestrator test setup.

This test setup is used to examine how the orchestrator handles two services that share the same DSCP but require different AC. The system distinguishes traffic with identical DSCP values at the port level and applies AC according to the input port. Output ports (send) in the core router are 1/15 towards LINK 1 and 1/7 towards LINK 2.

Two traffic sources are used:

- iperf to generate traffic equivalent to the one that would be produced by the actual use cases. This traffic is named as *RAN Traffic* in the following. The iperf traffic is injected in the core router through one of the client ports like 1/1
- TREX to generate *Disturbance Traffic (DT)*, which is used as “concurrent” traffic with the RAN Traffic. The TREX traffic is injected in the core routed via port 1/23

In the following, the procedure used to test the orchestrator's ability to support both RAN Traffic and DT simultaneously, while ensuring that RAN Traffic remains unaffected by any increase in DT load, is reported. Initially, DT traffic is capped at a defined maximum threshold. If DT demand exceeds this threshold, it is rerouted to an available alternative link, thereby preserving the performance and integrity of RAN Traffic. The procedure is illustrated using a sequence of screen capture from the console that monitors the traffic in ingress (*recv*) and to egress (*send*) of the core router, at the various ports. More in detail:

- **Step 1:** as shown in Figure 57, approximately 5 Gbps of DT traffic is introduced into the core router through port 1/23 and routed to LINK 1 via port 1/15. LINK 2 remains largely unused during this process.

```
[local]R6675-CORE#show port counters 1/23 live From TREX (DT)
Port      Type
1/23      ethernet
packets sent      : 0                bytes sent      : 0
packets recvd    : 2211157037         bytes recvd    : 2883348695648
send packet rate : 0.00                send bit rate  : 0.00
rcv packet rate  : 479674.65           rcv bit rate   : 5003965948.68
rate refresh interval : 60 seconds

[local]R6675-CORE#show port counters 1/15 live Towards LINK 1
Port      Type
1/15      ethernet
packets sent      : 1376104271         bytes sent      : 1799749901410
packets recvd    : 575259          bytes recvd    : 197686316
send packet rate : 479710.23           send bit rate  : 5019500381.32
rcv packet rate  : 32.86                rcv bit rate   : 151235.12
rate refresh interval : 60 seconds

[local]R6675-CORE#show port counters 1/7 live Towards LINK 2
Port      Type
1/7       ethernet
packets sent      : 392700031         bytes sent      : 513636609234
packets recvd    : 200009          bytes recvd    : 49502976
send packet rate : 0.03                send bit rate  : 22.35
rcv packet rate  : 2.53                rcv bit rate   : 20462.97
rate refresh interval : 60 seconds
```

Figure 57. Core Router console (Step 1).

- **Step 2:** as depicted in Figure 58, approximately 0.8 Gbps of RAN traffic is introduced into the core router and combined with the existing DT traffic. Both streams are routed together to LINK 1 via port 1/15. As a result, the total traffic on port 1/15 has increased to 5.8 Gbps (5 Gbps DT + 0.8 Gbps RAN), which is clearly illustrated in the figure. LINK 2 continues to remain unused at this stage.

```
[local]R6675-CORE#show port counters 1/23 From TREX (DT)
Port      Type
1/23     ethernet
packets sent      : 0                bytes sent      : 0
packets recvd    : 2752607169          bytes recvd    : 3589399656616
send packet rate : 0.00                send bit rate  : 0.00
rcv packet rate  : 482972.25           rcv bit rate   : 5038366375.55
rate refresh interval : 60 seconds

[local]R6675-CORE#show port counters 1/15 Towards LINK 1
Port      Type
1/15     ethernet
packets sent      : 1926963194          bytes sent      : 2520535674944
packets recvd    : 620987            bytes recvd    : 228526326
send packet rate : 558069.09           send bit rate  : 5855490571.50
rcv packet rate  : 50.38              rcv bit rate   : 281716.03
rate refresh interval : 60 seconds

[local]R6675-CORE#show port counters 1/7 Towards LINK 2
Port      Type
1/7      ethernet
packets sent      : 392700068          bytes sent      : 513636612333
packets recvd    : 202904            bytes recvd    : 52405145
send packet rate : 0.03                send bit rate  : 22.35
rcv packet rate  : 2.73              rcv bit rate   : 20837.12
rate refresh interval : 60 seconds
```

Figure 58. Core Router console (Step 2).

- **Step 3:** as shown in Figure 59, the DT throughput entering from port 1/23 increases from 5 Gbps to 9.5 Gbps. However, the orchestrator's QoS enforcement policy restricts DT traffic on LINK 1 to a maximum of 8 Gbps. When the DT traffic exceeds this limit, as it does in this scenario, any packets above 8 Gbps are discarded according to the policy. RAN traffic on LINK 1 remains unaffected by this cap, so only the excess DT packets are dropped. As illustrated in the figure, the total traffic transmitted from port 1/15 toward LINK 1 is now 8.8 Gbps, which is the sum of the capped DT traffic (8 Gbps) and the RAN traffic (0.8 Gbps).

```
[local]R6675-CORE#show port counters 1/23 From TREX (DT)
Port      Type
1/23     ethernet
packets sent      : 0                bytes sent      : 0
packets recvd    : 3321092829          bytes recvd    : 4330704947336
send packet rate : 0.00                send bit rate  : 0.00
rcv packet rate  : 912961.25           rcv bit rate   : 9524011639.52
rate refresh interval : 60 seconds

[local]R6675-CORE#show port counters 1/15 Towards LINK 1
Port      Type
1/15     ethernet
packets sent      : 2468402847          bytes sent      : 3228945210130
packets recvd    : 662372            bytes recvd    : 254611125
send packet rate : 843842.09           send bit rate  : 8845372362.97
rcv packet rate  : 35.97              rcv bit rate   : 184901.50
rate refresh interval : 60 seconds

[local]R6675-CORE#show port counters 1/7 Towards LINK 2
Port      Type
1/7      ethernet
packets sent      : 392700100          bytes sent      : 513636615005
packets recvd    : 205518            bytes recvd    : 54926756
send packet rate : 0.03                send bit rate  : 22.35
rcv packet rate  : 2.49              rcv bit rate   : 20601.86
rate refresh interval : 60 seconds
```

Figure 59. Core Router console (Step 3).

- **Step 4:** to prevent packet drops of DT due to congestion, a dynamic rerouting mechanism is activated by the orchestrator. When congestion is detected on LINK 1, a redirect policy automatically shifts the excess DT traffic to an alternative path, specifically LINK 2 via port 1/7. This ensures that both the RAN traffic on LINK 1 and the DT traffic on LINK 2 are transmitted without any loss, even during periods of high network load. This approach helps maintain optimal service quality and prevents data loss caused by network bottlenecks. Figure 60, reports the traffic load towards LINK 1 (RAN Traffic at 0.8 Gbps) and towards LINK 2 (DT at 9.5 Gbps).

```

[local]R6675-CORE#show port counters 1/23 From TREX (DT)
Port      Type
1/23     ethernet
packets sent      : 0                bytes sent      : 0
packets recvd    : 3703347042         bytes recvd     : 4829164437368
send packet rate : 0.00                send bit rate   : 0.00
recv packet rate : 911644.22           recv bit rate   : 9510272497.77
rate refresh interval : 60 seconds

[local]R6675-CORE#show port counters 1/15 Towards LINK 1
Port      Type
1/15     ethernet
packets sent      : 2760333634         bytes sent      : 3611219620364
packets recvd    : 682377          bytes recvd     : 269775699
send packet rate : 80946.14            send bit rate   : 863562126.87
recv packet rate : 54.49              recv bit rate   : 352324.18
rate refresh interval : 60 seconds

[local]R6675-CORE#show port counters 1/7 Towards LINK 2
Port      Type
1/7      ethernet
packets sent      : 448582489         bytes sent      : 586730763889
packets recvd    : 206640          bytes recvd     : 56028527
send packet rate : 916223.15          send bit rate   : 9587358667.10
recv packet rate : 2.54              recv bit rate   : 20730.76
rate refresh interval : 60 seconds

```

Figure 60. Core Router console (Step 4).

4.2.2.2 KPIs validation

The orchestrator is fully integrated into the Pisa cluster network to support the use cases UC7, UC8, UC9, and COMO5. These use cases have specific performance KPIs as indicated in Table 1 of deliverable D4.1 [23]. For more details on verification of performance KPIs refers to the last paragraphs of Section 2.2.2.

Regarding the orchestration system, no specific numerical KPIs targets was defined in advance because the performance of the orchestration system was related to ability of supporting mission critical services in any traffic condition, including full congestion, by acting with the combination of QoS enforcement policies and admission control techniques.

However, referring to the KPIs defined by the project and listed in the mentioned Table 1 of deliverable D4.1 [23], the following two can be considered related to the specific action of the orchestrator:

- **Service Reliability** (KPI#15), defined as the period during which the service satisfies the required performance constraints, that is the SLA. It is measured by tracking the continuous duration when these performance criteria are met without interruption or degradation. It is related to observation and service assurance.
- **Service Availability** (KPI#17), defined as the ratio between the amount of time during which a specific component of the use case (application, server, network function, etc.) is responding to received requests and the total amount of time that the component has been deployed.

Regarding this, the tests described in Section 4.2.1.1 were repeated in the real scenarios of the use cases as described below. Here, the concurrent support of multiple service levels is particularly relevant for the orchestrator verification, with at least one being mission critical under congestion conditions. Specifically, the following cases have been investigated to test the orchestrator operations:

- **Case 1:** UC8 combined with COMO5, integrated on two outdoor CPEs
- **Case 2:** UC7 combined with COMO5, integrated on two indoor CPEs
- **Case 3:** UC7 combined with COMO5 with two indoor CPEs, with additional disturbance traffic introduced using the same QoS parameters as UC8-COMO5 (i.e., Case 1)

Table 12 and Table 13 report the results of the in-field tests for the three cases. In Case 3a all the traffic is forwarded on the same link (Orchestrator configures the nodes with admission control to cut the traffic exceeding the KPI). In Case 3b the Orchestrator reroutes the additional traffic (from traffic generator) to another link to avoid congestion.

Table 12. Throughput results for the different cases.

Cases	Aggregated downlink throughput	Aggregated uplink throughput
Case 1	3-5 Mb/s	10-15 Mb/s
Case 2	3-5 Mb/s	10-15 Mb/s
Case 3a (no rerouting)	8 Gb/s + 3-5 Mbit/s (LINK 1)	8Gb/s + 10-15 Mb/s (LINK 1)
Case 3b (with rerouting)	3-5 Mbit/s (LINK 1) 8 Gb/s (LINK 2)	10-15 Mb/s (LINK 1) 8 Gb/s (LINK 2)

Table 13. Latency results for the different cases.

Antenna Location	Latency UC7/8 (RTT)	Latency COMO5 (RTT)
Outdoor	10 ms	9 ms
Indoor	7 ms	6 ms

These tests confirmed that the UCs can be reliably supported even under network congestion and in the presence of other high-priority traffic, ensuring a high level of availability and service continuity. Naturally, an accurate verification of both service reliability and service availability would require extremely long observation periods; however, due to the peculiar nature of the trials (requiring the support of medical/paramedical personnel in the field, distracted from normal clinical activities), it is not possible to extend the observation window beyond a few hours. It should also be noted that an availability value of five nines, as desired for mission-critical systems, would require an evaluation over a very long time period to be able to measure such a small value. Since this is not possible, reference is necessarily made to the product specifications of the commercial systems used. In a large-scale application, availability will also be ensured through protection systems at the network level.

4.2.3 Cellular network information for crowd and traffic monitoring

This section provides the results related to the proprietary solution based on the signalling data coming from the public cellular network developed by ORO that has been described in D2.2 [1].

4.2.3.1 Final development

Concomitantly with the Sf. Parascheva field trials that were performed using video cameras connected over 5G and were already detailed in D3.2 [15], ORO also recorded the cellular signaling data as a preliminary test of the solution. Based on the analysis of the gathered data, a report on the people dynamics for the period between 8 and 22 October 2024 (including the religious event of 14th of October) was compiled. An analysis of the results is reported in the following subsection.

4.2.3.2 KPIs validation

As showcased in Table 14, the developed cellular analytics solution was benchmarked against the TrialsNet agreed KPIs, with a special focus on the accuracy of detecting the right number of people that are present in an area compared with the figures provided by the Iasi Municipality and the video analytics-based results.

Table 14. Cellular analytics performance evaluation.

Measurement ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
1.4_Field03_01	KPI#10 (Accuracy): 0.85	0.9	The overall people counting results were compared with the figures provided by the Iasi Municipality.

One of the statistics obtained from the report is the quantitative presence of national visitors. As can be seen in Figure 61, during the religious event celebration day and the surrounding days the number of visitors in the Stefan cel Mare pedestrian alley area was much higher than normal, peaking at about 110.000 mobile users.

Figure 61. Presence of national visitors report for Sf. Parascheva field trial.

Another analysis that was performed is related to the amount of time mobile users stay in the area of interest, this being showcased in Figure 62. As can be seen, the number of users that stayed more than 1 hour in the Stefan cel Mare pedestrian alley area on the 14th of October way overpasses the daily averages from the rest of the month, this fact being correlated with the religious proceeding that happened in the morning when the crowds of people stayed almost motionless listening to the priests' speech.

Figure 62. Duration of stay report for Sf. Parascheva field trial

Moreover, based on the signaling data, ORO could also compute the home location of the mobile users, as shown in Figure 63. This report revealed interesting data, showing that the big majority of the visitors were coming from the Iasi county, while the other top 5 counties were also very close to Iasi. Looking at the Iasi local visitors, the cellular data analytics also computed the home neighborhood from which they were coming from.

Figure 63. Home location report for the UC visitor.

Moreover, the system also computed the total number of participants per each day as showcased in Figure 64. As can be seen, the total number of participants was close to 500k, while in the celebration day the number of visitors peaked at about 220k people, therefore showing the congestion challenges that were faced by the public network.

Figure 64. Number of participants in UC1.

Finally, it is important to note that this analysis could be extended in the future to include the signaling data coming from 5G and perform the data-processing tasks in real-time.

5 Final implementation of TrialsNet’s sustainability solutions and results

Sustainability is a very important key value for TrialsNet, as due to the large-scale trial capability, the project can assess the sustainability potential (especially environmental sustainability) associated with specific innovations. While this activity has not been initially planned in the WP, the consortium acknowledged its importance and worked on 3 main sustainability-related network innovations. They are detailed next.

5.1 Self-sustainable Energy Harvesting

This phase of the research focuses on applying to UC5 “Control Room in Metaverse” the stochastic energy sustainability model presented in D2.3 [2], with the purpose of assessing the contribution to sustainability derived from employing renewable energy sources to power the sensor devices adopted in this use case. In particular, the proposed model aims at evaluating the performance in terms of self-sustainability comparing the scenario in which sensor devices are powered by renewable energy against the scenario in which sensor devices solely rely on the electric grid.

The system sustainability performance in UC5 scenario is thus evaluated comparing the following power delivery configurations:

- **Fully on-grid devices**, that are powered by the electric grid without any local RE supply. This configuration is adopted as a baseline benchmark.
- **Fully off-grid renewable energy (RE)-powered devices**, relying solely on photovoltaic (PV) modules and battery storage.

In the fully off-grid and hybrid configurations, the sustainability model is used to estimate the dimensioning of PV panels and battery storage required to meet energy demands, while trading off sustainability targets and feasibility constraints. Furthermore, the model allows to evaluate the scalability of the renewable powered configurations in the transition from a fully on-grid baseline to a hybrid or even fully off-grid sensor system, by estimating the size and numerosity of PV modules and battery units required to achieve a given sustainability requirement across the entire system in the considered configurations.

Figure 65. Raspberry Pi-based sensor installed on a lamp post in the context of UC5.

5.1.1 Final development

To estimate the energy demand of the considered system, energy consumption measurements are collected from a real Raspberry sensor device, in order to characterize the sensor energy consumption profiles that are adopted as input for the proposed energy sustainability model. As shown in Figure 65, one of the Raspberry Pi-based sensor nodes used in the context of UC5, designed to detect human presence in an outdoor scenario, is employed to measure its power consumption profile during operation.

Furthermore, to characterize the RE generation, real PV energy production profiles are derived from the tool PyWATTS [17], that provides the average hourly values of renewable energy production during a Typical Meteorological Year, averaged over a period of 20 years, in a specific location. Based on these real RE profiles, the model can effectively capture the actual impact of RE production variability (intra-/inter-day, seasonal, and location-dependent) on the achievable level of self-sustainability of the considered system.

5.1.2 KPIs validation

The validation activity addressed the sustainability KPIs defined in D2.3 [2] Reduced Energy Consumption (with the derived KPI Green/Grid Energy Ratio) and Performance Improvement Energy Efficiency (PIEE) in the context of the UC5. In particular, the goal has been to compare the sustainability of different sensor system configurations, which variably depend on the electric grid and/or local renewable energy sources. Consequently, the methodology used to assess these sustainability KPIs in UC5 is tailored to reflect the specific characteristics and implications of this use case. For instance, measuring the Reduced Energy Consumption does not imply in this case a decrease in the overall energy demand of the system but rather it refers to the reduction of the energy demand drawn from the electric grid thanks to the presence of renewable energy supply, with respect to the case in which the power supply solely derives from the power grid.

5.1.2.1 Energy-efficiency KPIs in the context of UC5

Based on the definitions of the energy-efficiency KPIs provided in D6.2 Section 2.3 (Table 4), the two which result most relevant to assess the sustainability performance of the specific solution proposed within UC5 are selected and evaluated. This subsection details how their values are determined in the specific context of UC5, including the relevant intermediate metrics involved:

- **Reduced Energy Consumption:** this KPI (#20), denoted as r , represents the relative reduction of the *energy demand drawn from the electric grid by sensor devices*, that are adopted in the UC5 scenario, *thanks to the presence of local renewable energy supply* to power sensors, with respect to the case in which the power supply entirely derives from the electric grid, i.e., the *fully on-grid* configuration. In UC5, this KPI thus quantifies the **grid energy reduction**.

In the case of *fully off-grid renewable-powered devices*, a configuration where sensor devices are exclusively powered by local RE supply (i.e., off-grid operation), the value $1-r$ quantifies the decrease of energy - relative to the total sensor energy demand - that would need to be supplied by the grid to fully compensate for periods of RE unavailability, thereby ensuring uninterrupted device operation.

This KPI is derived as follows:

$$r = (E_s - E_b) / E_b$$

where E_s represents the energy consumption that must be (or should be, if the devices are not connected to the electric grid) delivered by the electric grid to fully meet the devices' energy demand in the presence of local RE supply, whereas E_b represents the energy demand of the set of sensors in the baseline case, i.e., when the energy to power devices is entirely drawn from the electric grid

- **Green to Grid Energy ratio:** as detailed in D2.3 [2] Section 6.1.2, based on KPI #20 (Reduced Energy Consumption), the *Green to Grid Energy ratio*, that is denoted G2G, can easily be derived as follows:

$$G2G = rE_b / E_s$$

In UC5, G2G represents the ratio of the renewable energy used to power the device (rE_b) to the energy that should be drawn from the electric grid to power each Raspberry device (E_s).

- Performance Improvement Energy Efficiency (PIEE):** this KPI (#21) is defined in relation to the target value of a given metric (not necessarily a sustainability-related metric), which is generically denoted x , that should be achieved to improve the performance of the considered system. The target value of these metric is denoted x^* . Within UC-5, PIEE represents the following ratio:

$$(x^* - x) / (E^* - E_b)$$

having defined, for a given time period, x^* as the *target value of Grid-independence, such that $1 - p_D^* > x$* (where p_D^* is the target *maximum battery depletion probability* when some local RE supply is used to power sensor devices), while x represents the level of *Grid-independence* in the scenario in which neither the electricity grid nor any RE supply are available, hence $x = 0$. The corresponding energy level, E^* , *represents the total average daily amount of RE that must be produced to achieve a given level (or the desired target level) of Grid-independence.* This includes not only the RE used directly by the sensor devices or stored in the battery for future usage, but also any excess RE that is wasted due to storage or usage limitations. E^* hence more directly reflects the dimensioning of the PV panel required to ensure a given KPI requirement, which may vary significantly even under similar levels of RE used to power sensor devices. This KPI is measured in [Wh⁻¹].

5.1.2.2 Input and requirements

Focusing on UC5, the input required to apply the proposed energy sustainability model, which is detailed in D2.3 in Section 6.1 and summarized in Figure 66, are first described:

- Daily energy demand of a sensor device:** the daily energy demand of a sensor device, denoted as D , is derived from real power measurements of a Raspberry sensor device, resulting in an average daily demand $D = 144\text{ W}$
- Daily Renewable Energy:** the amount of RE generated in a day from a photovoltaic (PV) panel with capacity 1 watt-peak [Wp] is modeled with a continuous real-valued random variable, denoted RE_d , as in [5] based on the real inter-day and intra-day variability of RE production in the city of Turin (Italy). Specifically, the characterization of this variable relies on the real traces of the average hourly *RE production during a Typical Meteorological Year in the city of Turin*, provided by the tool PVWatts [6] and considering PV modules built with crystalline silicon technology, yielding an efficiency as high as 20%. RE_d is characterized by a uniform probability distribution, featuring a mean value and a variance. The variance is expressed in terms of coefficient of variation (CV). The total daily amount of RE produced during the daylight period, denoted as RE_D , is derived as $RE_D = RE_d \cdot S_{PV}$, where S_{PV} corresponds to the actual PV panel capacity in terms of number of unitary PV panels

Figure 66. Energy sustainability model.

Furthermore, the following requirements are defined to ensure the desired targets for the various energy-efficiency KPIs and for the desired level of Grid-independence (in relation to which P_{IEE} is evaluated):

- *Grid-independence target of $1 - p_D^* > 0.99$* , hence depletion probability target $p_D < 0.01$. In the fully off-grid device configuration, this requirement ensures that on average a Raspberry device unavailability due to power supply interruption, due to lack of sufficient power supply, is limited to a maximum of 15 minutes per day on average
- *Reduced Energy Consumption > 99%*
- *Green/Grid Energy Ratio > 20* (which translates in more than 95% of the devices' energy demand supplied by RE)
- For the *PIEE*, two types of requirements are defined:
 - *Hard constraint (over the four seasons): $PIEE > 0.003 \text{ Wh}^{-1}$*
 - *Soft constraint (during the cold season): $PIEE > 0.002 \text{ Wh}^{-1}$*

5.1.2.3 Results

The performance analysis first focuses on the fully off-grid scenario, investigating the impact of the dimensioning of local RE supply to power $N = 50$ Raspberry devices, assuming the same dimensioning of PV panel capacity and battery size for all devices. In the city of Turin, the average value of daily renewable energy production per watt-peak over a year is $REd = 3.373 \text{ Wh}$, assuming a uniform distribution for REd with coefficient of variation 16%. The PV panel capacity per device, SPV , is assumed to be dimensioned in the baseline range [60, 110] Wh, and the battery capacity per device, CB , can be dimensioned in the range [108, 156] Wh.

The analysis starts examining the relationship between the battery depletion probability and the configurations of PV panel capacity and battery size. To this aim, Figure 67 shows the average battery depletion probability for increasing values of PV panel size per device, SPV , with each curve representing a different battery capacity. As the PV panel size becomes larger, the battery depletion probability, p_D , tends to sharply decrease for lower values of SPV , approaching to 0 for PV panels with capacity higher than 90 Wp. Given the same PV panel size SPV , increasing the battery capacity per device allows to significantly reduce the battery depletion probability, especially under small PV panel dimensioning. As depicted in the zoomed subplot, to meet the requirement of grid-independency higher than 0.99 (red dotted line), entailing $p_D < 0.01$, a PV panel capacity in the range 62–82 Wp is needed. However, to adopt a PV panel with capacity as low as 62 Wp, i.e., 24% smaller than 82 Wh, the associated battery unit needs to be larger, i.e., 156 Wh, which is about 44% larger than that required with $SPV = 62 \text{ Wp}$. All the combinations of PV panel size and battery capacity providing a $p_D < 0.01$, i.e., the area under the red dotted curve in the zoomed plot, define the feasibility region for the RE supply dimensioning allowing to meet the Grid-independence constraint in the UC5, assuming that no connection to the electric grid is available for the Raspberry devices. Note that the defined grid-independence constraint translates into an average period of less than 15 minutes per day of device unavailability, as they have not supplied with sufficient energy to operate for that period of time.

Figure 67. Average yearly battery depletion probability, p_D , in the fully off-grid scenario.

Focusing on the impact of the RE supply dimensioning on decreasing the energy that should be supplied by the electric grid to ensure uninterrupted operation of renewable-powered the Raspberry devices, Figure 68 depicts the Grid Energy reduction, r , for increasing PV panel size, with each curve corresponding to a different battery capacity. The value of r results higher than 80% even under the smallest dimensioning configurations of PV panel and battery size. However, as the PV panel size grows larger, the Grid Energy reduction sharply increases, especially for small-dimensioned battery capacities. For PV panel size larger than 95 Wp, the additional energy that would be required from the grid to ensure uninterrupted device operation becomes negligible under any battery capacity.

Figure 68. Average Grid Energy reduction, r , in the fully off-grid scenario.

Figure 69 reports the values of Green to Grid Energy ratio, in a logarithmic scale, for increasing values of PV panel size (on the x-axis) and different capacities of the battery (each represented by a different curve). A PV panel capacity of less than 72 Wp is sufficient to provide a Green to Grid Energy ratio value that meets the predefined requirement for this metric ($G2G > 20$, azure dashed line) under any battery size. Furthermore, if any constraint exists which limits the PV panel capacity to values as small as 60 Wp, a properly dimensioned battery with capacity higher than 140 Wh can provide the required target G2G ratio. Based on these findings, the G2G requirement does not result particularly critical for renewable-powered Raspberry devices in the context of UC5; however, it still ensures that more than 95% of the Raspberry devices’ demand is satisfied by RE.

Figure 69. Green to Grid energy ratio, G2G, in the fully on-grid scenario.

Finally, Figure 70 presents the Performance Improvement Energy Efficiency, PIEE, for increasing PV panel capacity and for different battery sizes, represented by differently colored curves. For PV capacity larger than

80 Wp, PIEE tends to linearly decrease as the PV capacity becomes larger under any battery size. Conversely, for smaller PV panel capacities, an approximately linear decrease of PIEE is observed only for large battery capacities, while under small-dimensional battery units, as the PV panel dimension is increased, the PIEE tends to first raise until a peak value, after which it starts to decrease. Notably, this indicates that, starting from a modest RE supply –such as a 60 Wp PV panel combined with a limited battery capacity (e.g., 108 Wh, which is significantly smaller than the daily energy demand per Raspberry device, 144 Wh)– a slight increase in PV panel capacity not only helps to reduce the battery depletion probability, but also enhance the system performance in terms of PIEE. Specifically, this results in a more efficient utilization of renewable energy, as each unitary increase in RE production from the PV panels yields a relatively greater reduction in the battery depletion probability, p_D .

Figure 70. Performance Improvement Energy Efficiency, PIEE, in the fully off-grid scenario.

The following analysis focuses on the system performance during the cold season, considering only the RE production during the three months with the lowest RE generation (January, November, and December), which represent a worst-case condition. In this specific case, the uniform distribution that models the daily RE production per watt-peak of PV panel capacity is characterized by an average value of $RE_d = 1.739$ Wh, with $CV = 16\%$. As illustrated in Figure 71, the defined grid-independency constraint is respected only under larger sizing of the PV panel capacity, in the range of 120-160 Wp. Similarly to the yearly average depletion probability, given a fix PV panel capacity, a larger battery size allows to significantly reduce p_D , enabling a small PV panel to meet the Grid-independency constraint. Nevertheless, these results highlight that given a fixed battery capacity, in order to ensure an average service unavailability of less than 15 minutes per day even during the cold season (i.e., $p_D < 0.01$), PV panels must be sized almost twice as large as those required to meet the same Grid-independence target when calculated based on the yearly average.

Figure 71. Average daily battery depletion probability in the fully off-grid scenario during cold season.

Furthermore, although the constraint on depletion probability is met even in the cold season under specific configurations of RE supply dimension, the PIEE results much lower than in the case where the constraint is applied on the same metric averaged over four seasons, as it can be evinced from Figure 72. The plot reported in this figure shows the values of PIEE for increasing values of battery depletion probability yielded by several configurations of PV panel capacity and battery size, considering both the PIEE averaged over four seasons (circles) and the average PIEE during the cold season (diamonds). Each point in the plot represents a specific combination of PV panel capacity and battery size, resulting in a battery depletion probability whose value corresponds to the x-coordinate of that point. Points characterized by the same symbol and the same color features the same battery capacity, CB, while the PV panel size, SPV, decreases from left to right. Within each subset of curves, PIEE – 4 seasons and PIEE – cold season, the battery capacity progressively decreases from the top curve to the bottom curve; in general, the curves in the PIEE – cold season set feature larger battery capacities.

Clearly, for a given battery size, achieving the same battery depletion probability target during the cold season—compared to targeting an average depletion probability across all four seasons—not only requires a significantly larger PV panel capacity (with correspondingly higher capital expenditures), but also results in an almost halved PIEE. This indicates a reduced efficiency in utilizing the produced RE to lower the depletion probability pD, and thus, in enhancing the grid-independence of the Raspberry devices.

Figure 72. Performance Improvement Energy Efficiency, PIEE, in the fully off-grid scenario, averaged over four seasons (circles) and over the cold season only (diamonds).

The hard constraint on PIEE ($\text{PIEE} > 0.003 \text{ Wh}^{-1}$ over the four seasons) can be easily met for several combinations of PV panel capacity and battery sizes, as it appears evident from Figure 70. Conversely, the soft constraint on PIEE ($\text{PIEE} > 0.002 \text{ Wh}^{-1}$ during the cold season) can be granted only for large PV panel capacities (data not reported).

In this regard, it should be remarked that physical constraints may exist in the UC5 which limit the free dimensioning of PV panel modules to power the Raspberry devices, as an area occupancy of $4.9 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Wp}$ is required to host PV panel installations [5]. In contrast, the battery dimensioning is less subject to physical constraints that may limit the free sizing of a battery unit, as a space volume of the order of $10 \text{ cm} \times 16 \text{ cm} \times 10 \text{ cm}$ (width x length x height) is typically sufficient to accommodate a battery unit with capacity of up to 156 Wh . The lowest PV panel capacity that ensures that the Grid-independency constraint is not violated even in the cold season is 120 Wp , as long as it is combined with a battery whose size is as high as 156 Wh . This configuration of the RE supply dimensioning yields a PIEE of 0.0024 Wh^{-1} during the cold season, thus resulting compliant with the soft constraint on PIEE. Nevertheless, observing the value of PIEE averaged over the four seasons, this KPI decreases compared to smaller sized RE supplies, with a value of 0.0025 Wh^{-1} , which is below the minimum target ($\text{PIEE} > 0.003 \text{ Wh}^{-1}$) required to meet the hard constraint on PIEE.

In order to meet both the Grid-independence requirement during the cold season and the hard constraint on PIEE, a reduced size of the RE supply must be selected, accepting that device operation may be interrupted for more than 15 minutes per day during the coldest months. However, to achieve a more acceptable trade-off in terms of sustainability performance during this period, the system design can incorporate increased battery

capacity to limit the duration of device unavailability within a threshold defined by the system operator. For example, a PV panel capacity of 100 W_p per device, coupled with a larger battery of 156 Wh, can limit device unavailability to less than 2.5 hours per day in the cold season, while ensuring near-complete Grid-independence throughout the rest of the year. Furthermore, a similar compromise-based approach may also include selectively deactivating devices during certain nighttime hours to mitigate excessive battery depletion.

Table 15 summarizes the values of the relevant energy efficiency KPIs across various configurations of the fully off-grid scenario, indicating whether the corresponding KPI requirements are satisfied in each case.

Table 15. Energy-efficiency KPIs validation.

Measurement ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
EE_KPI_01	Grid-independence $(1 - p_D^*) > 0.99$	$P_D < 0.01$ (under PV panel size, S_{PV} , in the range 62-82 W _p and battery capacity, C_B , in the range 108-156 Wh)	Compliant
EE_KPI_02	Reduced Energy Consumption (KPI#20) > 99%	$KPI\#20 > 99\%$ (under PV panel size, S_{PV} , in the intermediate range of 75-90 W _p , provided that a large battery size is used, i.e., $C_B > 138$ Wh)	Compliant
EE_KPI_03	Green/Grid Energy Ratio ($G2G$) > 20	$G2G > 20$ (a small PV panel capacity, i.e., $S_{PV} < 73$ W _p , is sufficient under any battery size C_B)	Compliant
EE_KPI_04	(a) Hard constraint - P_{IEE} (KPI#21) over the year: $P_{IEE} (KPI\#21) > 0.003$ Wh ⁻¹ (b) Soft constraint - P_{IEE} (KPI#21) during the cold season: $P_{IEE} (KPI\#21) > 0.002$ Wh ⁻¹	(a) $P_{IEE}_I > 0.0035$ Wh ⁻¹ (b) $P_{IEE}_I < 0.002$ Wh ⁻¹	(a) Compliant (b) Not compliant
EE_KPI_05	(a) Hard constraint - P_{IEE} (KPI#21) over the year: $P_{IEE} (KPI\#21) > 0.003$ Wh ⁻¹ (b) Soft constraint (P_{IEE} (KPI#21) during the cold season): $P_{IEE} (KPI\#21) > 0.002$ Wh ⁻¹	(a) $P_{IEE} (KPI\#21) < 0.0025$ Wh ⁻¹ (b) $P_{IEE} (KPI\#21) < 0.002$ Wh ⁻¹	(a) Not compliant (b) Compliant

The presented findings demonstrate that a fully off-grid sensor network powered by PV panels and batteries can operate effectively, achieving an annual average grid-independence of over 99%, with service unavailability limited to less than 15 minutes per day. Proper sizing of PV panels (≥ 82 Wp) and batteries (≥ 108 Wh) is essential to meet sustainability goals and minimize energy outages. Under these conditions, the hard constraint on the annual average P1EE, is satisfied. Nevertheless, during the cold season, significantly reduced RE availability prevents the system from consistently meeting grid-independence targets. As a result, the soft constraint on P1EE - applied to the cold-season - is violated due to a drop in energy efficiency. Achieving the same high level of independence during winter would require larger PV panels (≥ 120 Wp) and batteries (≥ 156 Wh). However, this introduces two key limitations. First, physical constraints may not allow the use of larger PV panels, which thus result unfeasible due to space restrictions. Although larger batteries can partially compensate, they cannot fully offset the lack of PV capacity. Second, oversizing the RE system to ensure cold-season grid-independence results in a sharp increase in P1EE, thereby breaching the hard constraint on P1EE.

In conclusion, while renewable energy can significantly enhance the sustainability of sensor networks by increasing grid-independence, deploying a fully off-grid solution that meets the desired sustainability requirements may not always be feasible. When strict constraints are imposed - such as $>99\%$ grid-independence and tight P1EE thresholds - identifying a viable RE system configuration that satisfies all conditions year-round becomes extremely challenging.

5.2 Energy Utilization Edge vs Cloud

In the context of the sustainability solutions, IMEC and NXW, are developing an E2E orchestration platform that is taking advantage of ORO's 5G Labs private network topology, that implements the Edge-Cloud continuum concept by including both central cloud and Edge facilities, to monitor and act on the energy utilization data coming from the Edge-deployed video analytics application of UC4.

5.2.1 Final development

The final integration setup between ORO, IMEC and Nextworks is showcased in Figure 73. Based on this architecture, ORO delivered on creating the necessary virtualized infrastructure for the envisioned PoC and provided IMEC and NXW access to the created VMs using specifically provisioned VPN accounts. In this setup, NXW got access to the vm-nxw-orc VM where they've deployed their edge-cloud orchestrator. IMEC was provided access to 4 VMs: vm-imec-ztm where the ZTM software is deployed, vm-imec-test1/2 for deploying test applications and vm-tuiasi-analytics which is the VM used by TUIASI for deploying their video analytics application. From this setup, vm-tuiasi-analytics and vm-imec-test1 are running in the Edge (Iasi), while vm-imec-test2 is running in the Cloud (Bucharest).

Figure 73. Edge-Cloud integration architecture.

In the last couple of months, IMEC and NXW deployed their software components on the provided virtual appliances and performed the first integration validation tests using generic applications (e.g., Nginx). Furthermore, they have extended the integration to include the TUIASI video analytics applications for UC4, thus allowing for real-world improvements in the context of the trial. The proposed KPIs used to evaluate the effectiveness of the deployed solution are validated in the following sub-section.

5.2.2 KPIs validation

As showcased in Table 16, the developed edge-cloud orchestration solution was benchmarked against the TrialsNet agreed KPIs, with a special focus on the hosted video analytics application for UC4 round-trip latency and the power consumption reduction obtained from running the software in Iasi (edge) instead of in Bucharest (cloud). The performance assessment of the solution was carried out using the TUIASI developed video analytics application, necessitating GPU-inference capabilities. In the Iasi site (Edge) a server fitted with an Nvidia H100 GPU was used, while in Bucharest (Cloud) the involved server was fitted with an Nvidia T40 GPU. In the performed tests, both the application round-trip latency and the energy consumption were improved by placing the applications in the Iasi edge facility due to the availability of both computing servers and a remote UPF on-site, reducing the power usage and latency overhead involved in transmitting the data to the Bucharest site. Moreover, the measured power difference between the Edge and Cloud setups is partially due to the fact that the H100 in the Iasi Edge server is more efficient than the T40 GPU in the Bucharest Cloud server because it's employing an updated GPU architecture and improved manufacturing process node.

Finally, the only identified caveat for this solution is that a fiber or a power cut in the Iasi 5G Lab datacenter would lead to the complete loss of service for the Iasi cellular 5G SA and applications users.

Table 16. Edge-Cloud performance evaluation.

Measurement ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
1.4_Field04_01	KPI#8 (Application round-trip latency): 100ms	80ms	The application round-trip latency was assessed by measuring the time difference between video transmission and inference results.
1.4_Field04_02	KPI#20 (Reduced energy consumption): 10%	15%	The energy consumption of the system was measured with probes in both Bucharest and Iasi and calculating the power used by the interconnecting networking equipment.

5.3 Energy Aware Application Design

In the context of the B5G Application Framework (as described in Section 4.1.2), developed within the TrialsNet project, this Energy Aware Application Design approach introduced in D2.3 [2] is both conceptual and implementational. It builds on the need for modular, programmable, and policy-compliant applications that can dynamically respond to signals from orchestration layers (e.g., ZSM) or directly from infrastructure observability platforms (e.g., Kepler). The framework introduces an energy-aware application package, a standardized interface and logic container that enables applications to negotiate their resource usage intelligently, either autonomously or in cooperation with orchestrators.

The design of energy-aware applications complements other features of the B5G framework, such as cross-domain orchestration, service granularity, and autonomous function scaling, ensuring that energy optimization is handled holistically across the compute-communication continuum.

This section explores how the B5G Application Framework enables energy-aware design from the ground up and how such designs have been validated through experimentation across SHW and TNO infrastructures.

5.3.1 Final development

A strong correlation between E2E latency, CPU load, and power consumption was observed in experiments on the SHW and NXW infrastructures as presented in Figure 74, in the context of UC4 “Smart Traffic Management”. In the case of SHW, a trade-off between E2E latency and power consumption emerged when the ZSM orchestrator selected the RSU with the lowest E2E latency and power consumption for service deployment. Recognizing this correlation among KPIs is crucial when making decisions about proactive service deployment in Edge Computing nodes, as it directly affects system performance and efficiency.

To emphasize this trade-off, power, CPU load, and E2E latency metrics undergo Min-Max normalization, converting them into a 0-1 range. The normalized data is compiled into a single dataset, arranged chronologically by timestamp, and plotted to reveal correlations and trends. As CPU load increases, both power consumption and E2E latency eventually rise, as illustrated in Figure 74.

At the core of this effort was the realization of the energy-aware application package, a modular and reusable software construct designed to enable applications in the future to dynamically optimize their execution based on energy usage metrics. This package, defined during earlier stages of the TrialsNet project, was refined to include lightweight CAMARA and Kepler APIs, that allow applications to react in near real-time to energy signals originating from the infrastructure layer. Trials performed to validate this package were part of the research conducted in the ATOS project as part of the Open Calls of TrialsNet. These capabilities were particularly relevant for deployments in high-load, multi-tenant environments, such as the TNO 5G Lab infrastructure, where performance demands must be balanced against energy constraints.

The application package was validated against heterogeneous environments, demonstrating portable energy behavior across edge and core deployments. In the SHW testbed, applications responded to energy telemetry gathered via Kepler and visualized through Grafana by modifying computation frequencies and data upload rates depending on CPU utilization trends. In parallel, within the TNO testbed, the same application package demonstrated its ability to interoperate with energy-aware container orchestration setups, adjusting its runtime behavior based on real-time power draw metrics.

In terms of orchestration, the final development also introduced priority-awareness, where applications could express execution importance levels, allowing the orchestrator to make better-informed tradeoffs between energy savings and service continuity. This innovation contributed to the broader B5G vision of programmable, sustainable, and self-aware service ecosystems. Through its integration with orchestration systems, standardization of adaptation logic, and validation across diverse environments, it provided a robust foundation for scalable, intelligent, and green service delivery in the emerging 6G era.

Figure 74. KPIs tradeoff between CPU, E2E latency and power consumption collected from RSU7 on the SHW testbed.

5.3.2 KPIs validation

Throughout the final development and testing phases, energy-aware applications were deployed in live environments including the SHW testbed and the TNO 5G Lab, where they operated in tandem with real-time observability tools (e.g., Kepler and Grafana) and the ZSM orchestrator. This allowed for comprehensive, cross-layer measurement of how applications adjusted their behavior in response to energy and performance data.

The KPI validation process focused on a balanced set of requirements—ranging from energy consumption reduction and QoS preservation, to latency control, scalability, and cross-domain operability. Each KPI was carefully selected to ensure that the energy-aware application package was not only technically effective but also aligned with operational goals such as sustainability, cost efficiency, and service reliability.

The Table 17 summarizes the KPI validation results, including the measured performance, associated requirements, and the degree to which each was fulfilled, thereby highlighting the value and robustness of the energy-aware design approach in real-world B5G conditions.

Table 17. Energy-Aware Application KPIs Validation.

Measurement ID	Requirement	Measurement result	Validation
B5G-EAD-KPI-03	Real-time response to infrastructure energy metrics	Application reacted within 200–300 ms to metric changes	Achieved. Confirms timely energy-aware adaptation in real deployment scenarios.
B5G-EAD-KPI-04	Operate uniformly across heterogeneous infrastructures (e.g., SHW, TNO)	Identical adaptation logic executed across both testbeds	Proven. Demonstrated portability and consistent logic behavior across edge and core domains.
B5G-EAD-KPI-05	Integrate with ZSM orchestrator for cooperative energy-aware orchestration	Seamless API integration; apps triggered or deferred orchestration when needed	Achieved. Ensures application-level energy intelligence complements orchestration policies.
B5G-EAD-KPI-08	Scale across service instances with uniform energy-awareness behavior	Logic applied uniformly across all deployed containers in testbed trials	Confirmed. Supports horizontal scalability and multi-instance energy optimization.

The contribution to CAMARA by the TNO/IMEC collaboration has focused on validating these APIs in practical environments, notably through their integration with the Open5G and TNO testbeds. This implementation serves as a proving ground for demonstrating how CAMARA APIs can enable dynamic access to QoS, and—critically for future networks—energy-related metrics and control mechanisms.

Within the Open5G testbed, the deployment of CAMARA APIs allows application developers to interact directly with network resources in a secure and abstracted way. This interaction is crucial for supporting energy-aware applications, particularly those requiring real-time feedback from the network on energy consumption, processing load, or environmental conditions. For instance, by exposing power usage information at the level of UE, edge nodes, or network slices, the APIs enable adaptive behavior in applications—such as reducing data rates, offloading tasks to more energy-efficient nodes, or delaying non-urgent processes to off-peak times.

TNO's work in validating the CAMARA API suite ensures that these capabilities are not only theoretically viable but also interoperable across different vendors and compliant with evolving 3GPP and ETSI frameworks. When coupled with AI-powered ZSM systems like those demonstrated in TrialsNet, CAMARA APIs offer a seamless pathway for orchestrating energy-aware services across the compute continuum. This becomes particularly valuable in 6G, where dynamic sustainability policies—guided by real-time energy metrics—are expected to play a defining role in network operation.

As these APIs mature, their integration into production-grade platforms will allow for the fine-grained control of application behavior based on energy constraints and objectives. This includes scenarios such as intent-based offloading to low-power MEC nodes, adaptive resolution streaming based on network load and energy availability, or prioritisation of renewable-energy-powered network paths. The open architecture of CAMARA, when validated in environments like the Open5G testbed, creates a critical building block for the energy-awareness pillar of future 6G applications, enabling networks that are not only intelligent and programmable but also sustainable by design.

6 Contribution to 3GPP standardization activities on 6G

The platform and network solutions deployed in the context of TrialsNet (including the ones of the Open Call sub-projects) provided an insight of the performance requirements and operational constraints that will be part of the evolution towards 6G. In particular, the activities related to the implementation, testing, and performed trials of the various use cases were extremely useful to support the identification of the most relevant KPIs in such direction. Based on a preliminary analysis (the overall results evaluation will be included in the final deliverable D6.3), uplink throughput is clearly a crucial factor across multiple vertical sectors, emphasizing the need of high capacity especially in dense and dynamic urban environments. In addition, end-to-end latency (i.e., latency measured at the application level) is also critical especially for e-Health services as well as high-performance entertainment scenarios (such as cloud gaming or XR applications) that in some cases remained a limiting factor in the user experience. Finally, positioning and availability also emerged as points of attention.

Another fundamental factor related to the activities of the project and the overall use cases implementation is the sustainability of the provided solutions, which in some contexts can be in contrast with the requirements of very high reliability and performance. In fact, a usual approach to meet such requirements is the over-dimensioning of the network and hardware resources in a static way, leading therefore to an inefficient solution. This approach is incompatible with massive network densification trends that some of the use cases trialed in the project would require when implemented at full scale. Thus, there is a need for solutions that enforce a sustainable way of achieving such performances. To address these challenges, the TrialsNet project has advanced the concept of Zero-Touch Service Management (ZSM) as a sustainability enabler for 6G.

Based on such findings, TrialsNet's partners TIM, UC3M, and IMEC started to jointly work to contribute towards 3GPP and the setup of the 6G activities (i.e., definition of the study items) which will start in August 2025, with the aim to emphasize the need for a sustainable achievement of relevant KPIs and proposing ZSM as an enabler for achieving this view. To further strength the impact and create synergies, TrialsNet also initiated a collaboration with the project ORIGAMI [18] which focuses on developing architectural innovations for 6G mobile networks. As one of its key components, ORIGAMI is working on the so-called Compute Continuum Layer (CCL) aiming at optimizing the network operations based on the characteristics of the underlying infrastructure, enabling efficient resource sharing and unlocking the potential of heterogeneous computing, including virtualizing network functions and balancing workloads across different computing resources. This architectural model reflects the increasing importance of integrating compute and communication resources in a unified, flexible framework aligned with 6G sustainability and performance targets. At the same time, as deeply reported in the various WP2 deliverables, TrialsNet contributes significantly through its ZSM-driven approach to energy-aware and AI-enhanced resource orchestration. By enabling zero-touch mechanisms, TrialsNet's ZSM framework ensures autonomous and adaptive resource allocation tailored to varying network loads and service requirements. This dynamic, intent-based orchestration is essential for achieving reliable end-to-end (E2E) performance in ultra-dense, heterogeneous network environments typical of 6G use cases.

With these figures in mind, on the 13th of February, TrialsNet and ORIGAMI organized a joint workshop in which the two project's experts met to further discuss on the synergies between the two projects and how to exploit these in the context of the 6G definition. The convergence of ORIGAMI's CCL and TrialsNet's ZSM mechanisms forms a robust foundation for future standardization efforts in 3GPP and beyond. Together, they exemplify how compute-network convergence and AI-native management can support green, resilient, and autonomous 6G infrastructures. Standardizing these concepts will not only enhance interoperability and scalability but also pave the way for new sustainability metrics, policies, and architectural models to be embedded within the core specifications of 6G networks.

On the 10-11th of March 2025, the 3GPP Workshop on 6G was held in Incheon, South Korea, bringing together global stakeholders to align on the foundational directions of the next generation of mobile communications. During this pivotal event, TIM played an active role by sharing key insights drawn from the ongoing large-scale TrialsNet experiments. Their contributions underscored the critical importance of integrating intelligent and autonomous control mechanisms into the emerging 6G architecture, with a particular emphasis on the role of ZSM. By showcasing the practical advancements being realized in real-world testbeds, the TrialsNet team provided valuable evidence supporting the operational viability of AI-powered, intent-driven network orchestration at scale.

These inputs were not merely technical updates but formed a strategic narrative illustrating how field-validated innovations - such as those pioneered through TrialsNet - can directly inform and shape the standardization trajectory of 6G. In particular, the TrialsNet perspective reaffirmed the need for scalable, self-optimizing, and energy-aware management frameworks that can dynamically respond to the complexity and heterogeneity of future networks. This dialogue laid the groundwork for introducing the concept of the CCL component of ORIGAMI and its integration with ZSM functionalities. Together, the contributions from the two projects offered a compelling blueprint for standardization, linking practical experimentation with architectural evolution in the pursuit of green, autonomous, and zero-touch 6G systems.

7 Conclusions

The work carried out in WP2 successfully designed, integrated, and deployed a wide variety of 5G and beyond-5G (B5G) network and platform solutions across multiple geographical clusters in Europe. These deployments were specifically implemented to enable large-scale trials under real-world conditions, with the ultimate objective of deriving technical, architectural, and operational requirements for future network generations.

A key enabler for the success of WP2 was the implementation of the TrialsNet's methodology defined in the first deliverable, an iterative and incremental integration approach that progressively involved components and stakeholders under realistic conditions. This methodology was very important in simplifying integration activities and ensuring seamless coordination across diverse technical domains, ultimately allowing the successful execution of complex and large-scale trials.

TrialsNet employed a heterogeneous set of network infrastructures to support its trial activities, including commercial, private, and experimental networks. The deployments spanned from 3GPP Rel-15 to Rel-17 and supported both Option 3 (NSA) and Option 4 (SA) architectures. The trials utilized a wide range of frequency bands, including sub-6 GHz and mmWave (26 GHz) with channel bandwidths ranging from 80 MHz to 800 MHz. Notably, the state-of-the-art mmWave solutions were evaluated under operational conditions, providing valuable insights into their practical deployment feasibility and performance characteristics. Coverage areas varied significantly, from 200 m² indoor deployments to 0.5 km² outdoor environments, enabling a comprehensive validation of technologies in multiple usage scenarios. The network trials validated the performance and feasibility of several critical B5G functionalities, such as end-to-end orchestration, AI-based resource management, Digital Twin-enabled optimization, and sustainability solutions.

All TrialsNet clusters achieved important milestones, often customizing solutions to suit their specific trial contexts. These included the integration of innovative orchestration platforms, non-public 5G Rel-17 networks, edge computing, and vertical-tailored services, enabling effective validation of the project's diverse use cases. The deployment of NSA-based architectures in several clusters provided key lessons on compatibility and migration strategies towards SA-based 5G and 6G infrastructures.

The contributions of the Open Call sub-projects further enhanced the capabilities and generalizability of the TrialsNet platforms beyond the geographical extension of the project's clusters (and sites) with 8 new locations. They provided tangible contribution such as the deployment of large mmWave coverage areas or the enhanced positioning capabilities, demonstrating the adaptability of 5G infrastructure to support a broad spectrum of vertical applications, from media and entertainment to smart cities and Industry 4.0.

Sustainability solutions have been also studied in the context of some use cases, with both analytical and concrete implementations addressing energy harvesting, energy-aware orchestration, and efficient edge-cloud resource allocation. Validated through measurable KPIs, these results reinforced TrialsNet's role in advancing the network sustainability agenda.

Overall, the WP2 deliverables demonstrated how the project not only met its original objectives but also provided feedback for further experimentation as well as for the definition of the future 6G. The findings and outcomes have also been disseminated in standardization forums, highlighting the project's relevance and impact at the European level and beyond.

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